

DECODING US TORT LIABILITY IN HEALTHCARE'S BLACK-BOX ERA: LESSONS FROM THE EU

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ABSTRACT

The rapid development of sophisticated artificial intelligence (AI) tools in healthcare presents new possibilities for improving medical treatment and general health. Currently, such AI tools can perform a wide range of health-related tasks, from specialized autonomous systems that diagnose diabetic retinopathy to general-use generative models like ChatGPT that answer users' health-related questions. On the other hand, significant liability concerns arise as medical professionals and consumers increasingly turn to AI for health information. This is particularly true for black-box AI because while potentially enhancing the AI's capability and accuracy, these systems also operate without transparency, making it difficult or even impossible to understand how they arrive at a particular result.

The current liability framework is not fully equipped to address the unique challenges posed by black-box AI's lack of transparency, leaving patients, consumers, healthcare providers, AI manufacturers, and policymakers unsure about who will be responsible for AI-caused medical injuries. Of course, the United States (US) is not the only jurisdiction faced with a liability framework that is out-of-tune with the current realities of black-box AI technology in the health domain. The European Union (EU) has also been grappling with the challenges that black-box AI poses to traditional liability frameworks and recently proposed new liability Directives to overcome some of these challenges.

As the first article to analyze the liability frameworks governing medical injuries caused by black-box AI in both the US and EU, we demystify the structure and relevance of foreign law in this area to provide practical guidance to courts, litigators, and other stakeholders seeking to understand the application and limitations of current and newly proposed liability law in this domain. We reveal that remarkably similar principles will operate to govern liability for medical injuries caused by black-box AI and that, as a result, both jurisdictions face similar liability challenges. These similarities offer an opportunity for the US to learn from the EU's newly developed approach to governing liability for AI-caused injuries. In particular, we identify four valuable lessons from the EU's approach: (1) a broad approach to AI liability fails to provide solutions to some challenges

posed by black-box AI in healthcare; (2) traditional concepts of human fault pose significant challenges in cases involving black-box AI; (3) product liability frameworks must consider the unique features of black-box AI; and (4) evidentiary rules should address the difficulties that claimants will face in cases involving medical injuries caused by black-box AI.

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INTRODUCTION

"I do not intend to deceive or mislead anyone, but I sometimes make mistakes or assumptions based on incomplete or inaccurate data. I also do not have the clinical judgment or the ethical responsibility of a human doctor or nurse." – ChatGPT¹

In April 2023, Open AI's ChatGPT-4 made headlines when it "passed the US [United States] medical licensing exam with flying colors."² It also "impressed and horrified" a physician when it matched his medical expertise by correctly diagnosing his patient with a rare medical condition using information from the patient's medical record.³ With more than 100 million users, ChatGPT's natural language responses to a wide range of

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¹ Hilary Brueck, *The Newest Version of ChatGPT Passed the US Medical Licensing Exam With Flying Colors — and Diagnosed a 1 in 100,000 Condition in Seconds*, INSIDER (Apr. 6, 2023), <https://www.insider.com/chatgpt-passes-medical-exam-diagnoses-rare-condition-2023-4>.

² *Id.*

³ *Id.*

inquiries and prompts have the potential to revolutionize the delivery of health information.⁴

In June 2023, a 29-year-old woman was awoken from her nap by her Apple watch when an alarm sounded to alert her that her heart rate had risen to 178 and remained high for over 10 minutes.⁵ At the hospital, she was diagnosed with a blood clot in her lungs and underwent life-saving surgery.⁶ The rise in wearable technology using artificial intelligence (AI) in combination with new health applications brings enormous potential for consumers to prevent and manage health conditions.⁷

Healthcare providers and consumers alike are turning more frequently to AI systems and models (collectively “AI”) to prevent, discover, monitor, and manage health conditions. For example, physicians may be tempted to turn to AI to answer clinical questions, provide medical information, or generate treatment documentation.⁸ Consumers, too, may try to save time and money by seeking quick answers to their medical questions and concerns from AI. In fact, a recent study found that when compared with human physicians, ChatGPT provided better quality and more empathetic responses to health questions posted in online fora.⁹ In addition to generative AI, like Open AI’s ChatGPT and Google’s Bard, which are developed to answer questions on a variety of general topics (called here “general-use AI”), AI can also be designed specifically for

⁴ See David Shepardson, *US Senate Leader Schumer Calls for AI Rules as ChatGPT Surges in Popularity*, REUTERS (Apr. 13, 2023), <https://www.reuters.com/world/us/senate-leader-schumer-pushes-ai-regulatory-regime-after-china-action-2023-04-13> (100 million users).

⁵ Shubham Singh, *Apple Watch Alerts High Heart Rate, Saves 29-Year-Old Woman’s Life From Fatal Blood Clot*, BUSINESS TODAY (Jun. 20, 2023), <https://www.businesstoday.in/latest/trends/story/apple-watch-alerts-high-heart-rate-saves-29-year-old-womans-life-from-fatal-blood-clot-386381-2023-06-20>.

⁶ *Id.*

⁷ See Madelyn Knowles et al., *Consumer Adoption of Digital Health in 2022: Moving at the Speed of Trust*, ROCKHEALTH (Feb. 21, 2023), <https://rockhealth.com/insights/consumer-adoption-of-digital-health-in-2022-moving-at-the-speed-of-trust>.

⁸ See Geoff Brumfiel, *Doctors Are Drowning in Paperwork. Some Companies Claim AI Can Help*, NPR (Apr. 5, 2023), <https://www.npr.org/sections/health-shots/2023/04/05/1167993888/chatgpt-medicine-artificial-intelligence-healthcare>; Michael DePeau-Wilson, *GPT-4 Is Here. How Can Doctors Use Generative AI Now?*, MEDPAGE TODAY (Mar. 20, 2023), <https://www.medpagetoday.com/special-reports/exclusives/103616>.

⁹ John W. Ayers et al., *Comparing Physician and Artificial Intelligence Chatbot Responses to Patient Questions Posted to a Public Social Media Forum*, 183 JAMA INTERNAL MED. 589 (2023). See Douglas Johnson et al., *Assessing the Accuracy and Reliability of AI-Generated Medical Responses: An Evaluation of the Chat-GPT Model*, RESEARCH SQUARE (Feb. 28, 2023), <https://www.researchsquare.com/article/rs-2566942/v1>.

healthcare (“health-specific AI”). For example, Microsoft Cloud for Healthcare, a suite of software designed to “improve the entire healthcare experience,” uses AI to “accelerate data-driven decision-making.”¹⁰ AI can also be trained to interpret medical images, diagnose diseases, and assist with minimally invasive procedures.¹¹

AI creates new possibilities for healthcare, including improving both access to care and patient outcomes, but it can also produce inaccurate medical information and recommendations, endangering patient safety. For example, the accuracy of an AI’s output is highly dependent on the quality of its training data, which can be limited or biased. Even with high-quality training data, AI may generate recommendations or decisions based solely on the patterns and correlations it detects in medical data while failing to consider other factors relevant to the patient’s health.¹² An alarming issue with large language models (LLMs), like ChatGPT, is their tendency to “hallucinate” fabricated information and present it to the user with a high level of confidence, which can be misleading and dangerous.¹³ The AI’s ability to produce inaccurate outputs is particularly worrisome when it comes to “black-box” AI, which operates without transparency or the ability to explain the basis for its recommendations or decisions. This is because when users cannot understand how or why the AI arrived at a particular recommendation or decision, it becomes difficult, or even impossible, for them to identify and correct potential errors in the AI’s output.

As black-box AI becomes increasingly integrated into healthcare, US courts will inevitably confront the task of examining complex liability issues that arise from medical injuries caused by such systems. The present tort framework governing liability for manufacturers and healthcare

¹⁰ Microsoft, *Microsoft Cloud for Healthcare*, MICROSOFT, <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/industry/health/microsoft-cloud-for-healthcare> (last visited Jul. 16, 2023); Tom McGuinness, *Microsoft Cloud for Healthcare: Empowering Healthcare to Deliver Meaningful Outcomes*, MICROSOFT (Apr. 12, 2023), <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/industry/blog/healthcare/2023/04/12/microsoft-cloud-for-healthcare-empowering-healthcare-to-deliver-meaningful-outcomes/>.

¹¹ FOOD & DRUG ADMIN, *Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning (AI/ML)-Enabled Medical Devices*, <https://www.fda.gov/medical-devices/software-medical-device-samd/artificial-intelligence-and-machine-learning-aiml-enabled-medical-devices> (current as of Oct. 5, 2022); Daichi Kitaguchi, et al., *Artificial Intelligence-Based Computer Vision in Surgery: Recent Advances and Future Perspectives*, 6 ANN GASTROENTEROL SURG. 29 (2022).

¹² See Rich A. Caruana, et al., *Intelligible Models for Healthcare: Predicting Pneumonia Risk and Hospital 30-Day Readmission*, PROCEEDINGS OF THE 21TH ACM SIGKDD INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON KNOWLEDGE DISCOVERY AND DATA MINING. ASSOCIATION FOR COMPUTING MACHINERY 1721 (2015) (AI confused correlation with causation in risk evaluation).

¹³ See Brueck, *supra* note 1; Brumfiel, *supra* note 8.

providers is often insufficient to address the unique challenges posed by black-box AI used in healthcare because it is not always possible to sufficiently link a black-box AI's injury-causing output to the actions of a legally responsible party. This is in contrast to transparent and interpretable "white-box" AI, which allows developers and users to understand the AI's reasoning process and evaluate its output, making it possible to trace injuries to the actions of manufacturers and/or healthcare providers under the existing liability framework.

Across the pond, the European Union (EU) has been grappling with similar challenges that AI poses to the existing frameworks that govern liability of manufacturers and healthcare providers. In an effort to address these liability challenges, the European Commission (EC) recently proposed two Directives: a *Directive on Liability for Defective Products* (Proposed Product Liability Directive – PLD)¹⁴ and a *Directive on Adapting Non-contractual Civil Liability Rules to Artificial Intelligence* (Proposed AI Liability Directive – AILD).¹⁵ This article argues that, given the similarities in the basic liability frameworks in the US and the EU and the shared liability challenges that black-box AI poses in cases involving medical injuries, the EU's approach to AI liability can provide valuable insights as courts, litigators, and other stakeholders, including policymakers, manufacturers, and healthcare providers, in the US begin to confront the challenges raised by black-box AI in healthcare.

This article is the first to provide an in-depth comparative analysis of the issue of liability for medical injuries caused by black-box AI in both the US and the EU to provide a practical guide for US courts, AI manufacturers, healthcare providers, patients, or anyone else seeking to understand the application and limitations of the liability law in this domain. It consists of five Parts.

Part I provides an introduction to black-box AI in healthcare. It sketches the current state of AI in the health domain and explains the technical characteristics of various types of AI in an easily-understandable fashion. It also provides specific examples of different types of AI currently in use and forecasts AI's future potential health-related uses.

Part II identifies and examines the current tort liability framework applicable to cases involving medical injuries caused by black-box AI in the US. It discusses the legal elements required to hold manufacturers and

¹⁴ *Commission Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on Liability for Defective Products*, COM(2022) 495 final (Sept. 28, 2022) [hereinafter proposed PLD].

¹⁵ *Commission Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on Adapting Non-Contractual Civil Liability Rules to Artificial Intelligence (AI Liability Directive)*, COM(2022) 406 final (Sept. 28, 2022) [hereinafter proposed AILD].

healthcare providers liable in such cases and reveals that the existing framework struggles to govern some medical injuries caused by black-box AI. In particular, it exposes three main weaknesses in the current tort liability framework relating to: (1) legal standards used to determine product defects, (2) identification of fault by a legally responsible party, and (3) burden of proof rules.

Part III identifies and analyzes the current and proposed liability framework applicable to cases involving medical injuries caused by black-box AI in the EU. It first outlines the general liability principles that would govern manufacturer and healthcare provider liability for such injuries in the EU under the current framework. It then provides an overview of the newly proposed PLD and AILD and their potential impact on liability for medical injuries caused by black-box AI. Part III reveals that the EU's basic liability framework uses legal principles remarkably similar to those in the US by generally anchoring manufacturer liability on product defects and healthcare provider liability on fault. As a result, the EU's newly proposed Directives, which are aimed at addressing the liability challenges caused by black-box AI, can provide important lessons as various stakeholders confront similar challenges in the US.

Part IV aims to discover valuable insights from the EU's approach by analyzing liability in three hypothetical scenarios involving a medical injury caused by black-box AI under both US and EU law. The comparative analysis of these three scenarios reveals that liability gaps can manifest in both jurisdictions when a medical injury results from a healthcare provider's use of an autonomous black-box AI (Scenario 1), a nonautonomous black-box AI (Scenario 2), and a consumer's use of a general black-box generative AI (Scenario 3). These gaps are likely to occur when the AI's noninterpretable reasoning process produces an injury-causing output, and the following are true: (1) the AI was functioning as designed by the manufacturer, (2) the manufacturer complied with safety regulations relating to the AI's development and marketing, and (3) individual and organizational healthcare providers were reasonable in their selection and implementation of the AI and could not have reasonably known that the AI's output was incorrect. In addition, black-box AI's complex architecture and operation present evidentiary challenges for injured claimants.

Part V identifies lessons learned from the EU's approach to AI liability in the context of medical injuries caused by black-box AI. It first highlights that the EU's approach is relevant because the liability frameworks in both jurisdictions operate under similar legal principles and face common legal challenges when confronted with black-box AI in the healthcare domain. It then identifies four lessons learned from the EU's approach that may help address these common challenges: (1) a broad

approach to AI liability fails to provide solutions to some challenges posed by black-box AI in healthcare; (2) traditional concepts of human fault pose significant challenges in cases involving black-box AI; (3) product liability frameworks must consider the unique features of black-box AI; and (4) evidentiary rules should address the difficulties that claimants will face in cases involving medical injuries caused by black-box AI.

I. BLACK-BOX AI IN HEALTHCARE

AI refers broadly “to the ability of machines to perform tasks that would normally require human-level intelligence.”¹⁶ While AI design and architecture can be complex and wide-ranging, a basic understanding of AI and its applications is required. Thus, this Part first explains the key characteristics of AI in healthcare and then discusses healthcare provider and direct-to-consumer uses.

A. CHARACTERISTICS OF AI IN HEALTHCARE

AI can be described as “*autonomous*” to mean that a human does not review or oversee their output or “*non-autonomous*” to indicate that a human exercised some review or oversight of the AI’s output.¹⁷ AI can also be designed with various levels of complexity. “*White-box*” AI is designed to be transparent and interpretable such that the developer and user are able to access and understand the logic underlying the AI’s output. The simplest white-box AI receives an input and follows an explicit set of pre-programmed “if-then” rules to produce an output.¹⁸ More complex white-box AI can be designed using *machine learning*, which involves training an AI with large amounts of data so that it can learn and improve its performance based on patterns and relationships in the data and without explicit rules.¹⁹

¹⁶ Prathamesh Thakare, *The Future is Now: A Look at the Most Promising Emerging Technologies*, SCRRUM (Jan. 1, 2023), <https://scrrum.com/blog/look-at-the-most-promising-emerging-technologies>.

¹⁷ Michael D. Abramoff et al., *Automated and Computer-Assisted Detection, Classification, and Diagnosis of Diabetic Retinopathy*, 26 *TELEMEDICINE & E-HEALTH* 544, 545 (2020); but see Mindy N. Duffourc, *Malpractice by the Autonomous AI Physician*, 2023 *U. ILL. J. L. TECH. & POL.* 1 (2023) (noting a more dynamic approach to levels of automation and autonomy).

¹⁸ KARTIK HOSANAGAR, *A HUMAN’S GUIDE TO MACHINE INTELLIGENCE: HOW ALGORITHMS ARE SHAPING OUR LIVES AND HOW WE CAN STAY IN CONTROL* 106 (Penguin Books 2020).

¹⁹ Oriol Pujol, *The Concept of “AI” Opacity and Societal Impact in ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND THE LAW* 28 (Pablo Garcia Mexia & Francisco Pérez Bes eds., 2021).

Even more complex is AI that uses a subset of machine learning called *deep learning*. Deep learning enables AI to make decisions by training artificial neural networks with large datasets. Deep-learning AI is usually referred to as “black-box” AI because it uses complex algorithmic reasoning that makes it extremely difficult or impossible to understand how the AI arrived at its output, making it noninterpretable.²⁰ Although computer scientists can explain the complex technical components used to design deep-learning AI, even they cannot truly understand exactly why a black-box AI produces a particular output.²¹ Noninterpretability is especially concerning for “adaptive” black-box AI, which, instead of being “locked” when placed on the market to ensure that it produces the same output in response to the same input, can continue to learn as it collect new data while in use.²² Generative AI is a type of “black-box” AI that uses deep learning algorithms to recognize characteristics and patterns in vast amounts of data to create new content, such as text and images.²³

Although the complexity of black-box AI makes it noninterpretable and often more unpredictable, this complexity also enables the AI to be more accurate and solve more complex problems.²⁴ Still, the combination of black-box AI’s capacity to produce erroneous information and humans’ inability to understand how it generated such outputs is a significant source of concern. As a result, there are efforts to make black-box AI “explainable.”²⁵ *Explainable AI* involves using a second explanatory white-box algorithm that can approximate the output of the black box and provide

²⁰ Sara Gerke, *Health AI for Good Rather Than Evil? The Need for a New Regulatory Framework for AI-Based Medical Devices*, 20 *Yale J. Health Pol’y, L., & Ethics* 433, 445 (2021); Kun-Hsing Yu et al., *Artificial Intelligence in Healthcare*, 2 *Nature Biomed. Eng’g* 719, 720 (2018).

²¹ See Jason Yosinski et al., *Understanding Neural Networks Through Deep Visualization*, in *DEEP LEARNING WORKSHOP*, 31ST INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MACHINE LEARNING (2015).

²² FOOD & DRUG ADMIN., *Proposed Regulatory Framework for Modifications to Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning (AI/ML)-Based Software as a Medical Device (SaMD): Discussion Paper and Request for Feedback* (2019) [hereinafter FDA Discussion Paper], <https://www.fda.gov/files/medical%20devices/published/US-FDA-Artificial-Intelligence-and-Machine-Learning-Discussion-Paper.pdf>.

²³ See Open AI, *Generative Models*, OPEN AI (June 16, 2016), <https://openai.com/research/generative-models>.

²⁴ Charlotte Tschider, *Medical Device Artificial Intelligence: The New Tort Frontier*, 46 *BYU L. REV.* 1551, 1561–62 (2021).

²⁵ See Guang Guang Yang et al., *Unbox the Black-Box for the Medical Explainable AI via Multi-Modal and Multi-Centre Data Fusion: A Mini-Review, Two Showcases and Beyond*, 77 *INFO. FUSION* 29, 30 (2022) (noting that as the layers of ANNs grow deeper, the AI’s algorithmic reasoning process becomes opaquer and difficult for humans to understand).

a post hoc explanation of the AI's output.²⁶ However, this explanation may not always be the true reason for the AI's output, which is often concealed from even the AI's creators.²⁷

B. HEALTHCARE PROVIDER AND DIRECT-TO-CONSUMER USES

Black-box AI is increasingly developed to be used by healthcare providers and consumers. The following first discusses black-box AIs that are used by healthcare providers and then those that are directly addressed to consumers.

1. HEALTHCARE PROVIDER USE

Black-box AI can perform a wide range of healthcare tasks, from helping providers position patients for CT scans²⁸ to diagnosing medical conditions.²⁹ To date, the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) has permitted marketing of more than 520 AI-based medical devices, many of which are black-box AI that use deep learning algorithms.³⁰ In addition to health-specific AI, healthcare providers may also turn to general-use AI, like ChatGPT, to obtain medical information.

a. Health-Specific AI

Currently, most legally-marketed black-box AIs are non-autonomous and intended to assist, but not replace, clinical decision making. Such devices can help radiologists interpret mammograms³¹,

²⁶ Boris Babic, et al., *Beware Explanations From AI in Health Care*, 373 *SCIENCE* 284 (2021); Sara Gerke, "Nutrition Facts Labels" for Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning-Based Medical Devices—The Urgent Need for Labeling Standards, 91 *GEO. WASH. L. REV.* 79, 83 (2023).

²⁷ See Sources cited *id.*

²⁸ Yadong Gang, et al., *A Comparison Between Manual and Artificial Intelligence-Based Automatic Positioning in CT Imaging for COVID-19 Patients*, 31 *EUR. RADIOL.*, 6049 (2021).

²⁹ See Huiying Liang, et al. *Evaluation and Accurate Diagnoses of Pediatric Diseases Using Artificial Intelligence*, 25 *NATURE MED.*, 433 (2019).

³⁰ *FOOD & DRUG ADMIN*, *supra* note 11; Gerke, *supra* note 26.

³¹ Letter from Thalia T. Mills, Dir. Div. of Radiological Health, U.S. Food & Drug Admin. to Juliane Dinter, Visage Imaging GmbH (Dec. 21, 2020), https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/cdrh_docs/pdf20/K201411.pdf.

cardiologists evaluate coronary artery disease³², surgeons detect colorectal polyps³³, and physicians assess musculoskeletal disease.³⁴

Autonomous medical AI makes medical decisions without the involvement of a human medical expert.³⁵ In some cases, a black-box AI might have the technical ability to be autonomous but is classified as non-autonomous because the manufacturer's instructions for use require human expert involvement. For example, Viz ICH is a legally-marketed black-box AI that detects intracranial hemorrhages in CT scans and quickly notifies specialists of positive findings.³⁶ VIZ ICH's analysis of the CT scans occurs in conjunction with the standard workflow involving human analysis of the same scans.³⁷ While using the VIZ ICH allows for quicker detection of intracranial hemorrhages and referral to a specialist, it does not replace the human radiologist's first-line analysis.³⁸ However, this same AI would be considered autonomous if it provided the sole first-line analysis of the CT scans. For example, in Europe, Chestlink was the first autonomous medical AI to receive a CE mark. Unlike VIZ ICH's analysis of CT scans, Chestlink uses deep learning to analyze chest X-rays and produce radiology reports

³² Letter from Stephen C. Browning -S, Assistant Dir. Div. of Cardiac Electrophysiology, Diagnostics and Monitoring Dev, U.S. Food & Drug Admin. to Kelliann Payne, KeyaMed NA Inc. (Mar. 1, 2022), https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/cdrh_docs/pdf21/K213657.pdf.

³³ Letter from Shanil P. Haugen -S, Assistant Dir. Div. of Renal, Gastrointestinal, Obesity and Transplant Devices, U.S. Food & Drug Admin. to John Smith, Chengdu Wision Medical Device Co., LTD (Nov. 18, 2021), https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/cdrh_docs/pdf21/K211326.pdf.

³⁴ Letter from Thalia T. Mills, Dir. Div. of Radiological Health, U.S. Food & Drug Admin. to M. Alaine Medio, Siemens Medical Solutions USA, Inc. (Feb. 20, 2020), https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/cdrh_docs/pdf19/K193267.pdf.

³⁵ See Michael D. Abramoff et al., *Pivotal Trial of an Autonomous AI-Based Diagnostic System for Detection of Diabetic Retinopathy in Primary Care Offices*, 1 NPJ DIGITAL MED. 39 (2018) (noting that an autonomous AI interprets retinal images without a human expert).

³⁶ Stavros Mtsoukas et al., *Pilot Deployment of Viz-Intracranial Hemorrhage for Intracranial Hemorrhage Detection: Real-World Performance in a Stroke Code Cohort*, STROKE (Jul. 11, 2022), <https://www.ahajournals.org/doi/10.1161/STROKEAHA.122.039711>; Letter from Thalia T. Mills, Dir. Div. of Radiological Health, U.S. Food & Drug Admin. to Gregory Ramina, Viz.ai, Inc. (Mar. 2, 2020), https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/cdrh_docs/pdf19/K193658.pdf.

³⁷ *Id.*

³⁸ See Letter from Thalia T. Mills, Dir. Div. of Radiological Health, U.S. Food & Drug Admin. to Gregory Ramina, *supra* note 36, (noting that the algorithm analyzes images “in parallel to standard of care image interpretation”).

without the involvement of a human radiologist in the first-line analysis.³⁹ As a result, AI is already capable of analyzing radiology films without human expert involvement.

To date, IDx-DR (rebranded as LumineticsCore) is the only black-box autonomous medical AI that has been reviewed by the FDA and authorized for use in clinical practice.⁴⁰ IDx-DR uses deep learning to diagnose diabetic retinopathy, a sight-threatening eye condition, without input or oversight by a human ophthalmologist.⁴¹ This allows healthcare providers without ophthalmological expertise to screen patients for diabetic retinopathy using IDx-DR, enabling early disease detection and management.⁴²

As AI technology continues to advance and the growth of big data accelerates, autonomous black-box AI is expected to increase.⁴³ Autonomous deep learning AI that can screen for hard-to-catch heart conditions⁴⁴, analyze CT scans to provide early diagnosis of pleural diseases⁴⁵, and analyze images of skin lesions to classify skin cancer⁴⁶ promises improved diagnostic timing and accuracy, less invasive medical procedures, increased access to treatment, and lower treatment costs.⁴⁷

³⁹ See OXIPIT, *Autonomous AI Medical Imaging: Understanding ChestLink*, OXIPIT (Apr. 5, 2022), <https://oxipit.ai/news/autonomous-ai-medical-imaging-understanding-chestlink> (regarding Chestlink's CE mark and autonomy); OXIPIT, *Product: Chestlink, ChestEye*, <https://www.ai4hlth.org/product-profiles/Oxipit> (last visited Jul. 16, 2023) (regarding chest link's development using deep learning).

⁴⁰ FOOD & DRUG ADMIN, DE NOVO CLASSIFICATION REQUEST FOR IDX-DR, https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/cdrh_docs/reviews/DEN180001.pdf; Digital Diagnostics, *Digital Diagnostics Sheds Light on AI Tech with LumineticCore Product Rebrand* (Mar. 28, 2023), DIGITAL DIAGNOSTICS, <https://www.digitaldiagnostics.com/newsroom/digital-diagnostics-sheds-light-on-ai-tech-with-lumineticcore-product-rebrand>.

⁴¹ Press Release, U.S. Food & Drug Admin., *FDA Permits Marketing of Artificial Intelligence-Based Device to Detect Certain Diabetes-Related Eye Problems* (Apr. 11, 2018), <https://www.fda.gov/news-events/press-announcements/fda-permits-marketing-artificial-intelligence-based-device-detect-certain-diabetes-related-eye>.

⁴² *Id.*

⁴³ Jordan Zheng et al., *Machine Learning in Medicine: What Clinicians Should Know*, 64 SINGAPORE MED. J. 91 (2021).

⁴⁴ Soonil Kwon et al., *Deep Learning Approaches to Detect Atrial Fibrillation Using Photoplethysmographic Signals: Algorithms Development Study*, 7 JMIR MHEALTH AND UHEALTH e12770 (2019).

⁴⁵ Neslihan Ozcelik et al., *Deep Learning for Diagnosis of Malign Pleural Effusion on Computed Tomography Images*, 78 CLINICS 100210 (2023).

⁴⁶ Andre Esteva et al., *Dermatologist-Level Classification of Skin Cancer with Deep Neural Networks*, 542 NATURE 115 (2017).

⁴⁷ See, e.g., Zheng, et al., *supra* note 43; Walker Morrell et al., *The Oversight of Autonomous Artificial Intelligence: Lessons From Nurse Practitioners as Physician Extenders*, 9 J.L. & BIOSCI. LSAC021 (2022).

b. General-Use AI

Healthcare providers might also use general-use AI to help them with a variety of tasks, ranging from email drafting to diagnosis and treatment planning.⁴⁸ According to a physician and former CEO of Kaiser Permanente, “[n]o physician who practices high-quality medicine will do so without accessing ChatGPT or other forms of generative AI.”⁴⁹ However, physicians’ growing interest in using generative AI concerns bioethicists who “worry that doctors will turn to the bot for advice when they encounter a tough ethical decision.”⁵⁰

Nevertheless, there is evidence that doctors and medical students are already using ChatGPT to answer clinical questions, and when tested, ChatGPT was able to “produce a correct diagnosis accurately at close to the level of a third- or fourth-year medical student.”⁵¹ Of course, if ChatGPT provides accurate information, using this tool may indeed assist with a quick diagnosis. Though ChatGPT has shown some promise in the area of medical diagnosis, it has also made critical errors by omitting relevant differential diagnoses.⁵² Finally, the confidence and sophistication with which ChatGPT responds to inquiries is troubling, given its ability to give fake information, often referred to as “hallucination.”⁵³

2. DIRECT-TO-CONSUMER USE

Black-box AIs are also increasingly developed for consumers as their primary target audience rather than healthcare providers. Those direct-to-consumer (DTC) AI tools can be health-specific, such as health apps or patient monitoring devices, but there are also general-use AIs like ChatGPT that consumers may consult for medical help.

⁴⁸ See Brumfiel, *supra* note 8. Andrea Koncz, *6 Potential Medical Use Cases For ChatGPT*, TMF (Dec. 19, 2022), <https://medicalfuturist.com/6-potential-medical-use-cases-for-chatgpt>; *What Can ChatGPT Do for Healthcare Practices*, ENTREPRENEUR, (May 2, 2023), <https://www.entrepreneur.com/science-technology/what-can-chatgpt-do-for-healthcare-practices/450626>.

⁴⁹ Khari Johnson, *ChatGPT Can Help Doctors – and Hurt Patients*, WIRED (Apr. 24, 2023), <https://www.wired.com/story/chatgpt-can-help-doctors-and-hurt-patients>.

⁵⁰ *Id.*

⁵¹ Brumfiel, *supra* note 8.

⁵² Stephen Hughts, *How Good Is ChatGPT at Diagnosing Disease? A Doctor Puts It Through Its Paces*, THE CONVERSATION (Apr. 27, 2023), <https://theconversation.com/how-good-is-chatgpt-at-diagnosing-disease-a-doctor-puts-it-through-its-paces-203281>.

⁵³ Homolak J., *Opportunities and Risks of ChatGPT in Medicine, Science, and Academic Publishing: A Modern Promethean Dilemma*, 64 CROAT. MED. J. 1 (2023).

a. Health-Specific AI

Consumers are more and more likely to turn to digital health resources like wearable technology and health apps for health-related information, management, and monitoring.⁵⁴ While the majority of health apps and wearables focus on general wellness and activity tracking, there is an increase in the development of DTC health technology aimed at managing health conditions, such as mental health disorders, diabetes, digestive diseases, and heart conditions.⁵⁵

Many of these DTC digital health technologies are AI-driven.⁵⁶ Of these, some are black-box AI, including applications that can interpret at-home ECG's and provide users with "instant determinations of multiple cardiac conditions"⁵⁷ and identify irregular heart rhythms.⁵⁸ The availability of DTC black-box AI for healthcare will only continue to grow as big data and machine learning technology advance. Google recently released an open-source software suite to facilitate the development of digital health apps.⁵⁹ In the future, consumers might use a health-specific LLM to answer medical questions⁶⁰ or deep-learning wearable technology to detect early stroke symptoms.⁶¹

b. General-Use AI

⁵⁴ Knowles, *supra* note 7 (noting increased adoption of digital health technology); *Digital Health Trends*, IQVIA, <https://www.iqvia.com/-/media/iqvia/pdfs/institute-reports/digital-health-trends-2021/iqvia-institute-digital-health-trends-2021.pdf> (last visited Jul. 17, 2023) (noting more than 350,000 digital health apps available to consumers as of 2021).

⁵⁵ *Id.* at 8.

⁵⁶ Sara Gerke & Delaram Rezaeikhonakdar, *Privacy Aspects of Direct-to-Consumer Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning Health Apps*, 6 INTELLIGENCE-BASED MED. 100061 (2022).

⁵⁷ IQVIA, *supra* note 54, at 26; *FDA Clears First of its Kind Algorithm Suite for Personal ECG*, AliveCor (Nov. 23, 2020), https://www.alivecor.com/press/press_release/fda-clears-first-of-its-kind-algorithm-suite-for-personal-ecg.

⁵⁸ Letter from Jennifer Shih Kozen, Asst. Dir. Div. of Cardiac Electrophysiology, U.S. Food & Drug Admin. to Luke Olson, Apple Inc. (Jun. 3, 2022), https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/cdrh_docs/pdf21/K213971.pdf.

⁵⁹ Heather Landi, *Google Launches Open Health Stack for App Developers, Unveils New AI Partnerships*, FIERCE HEALTHCARE (Mar. 14, 2023), <https://www.fiercehealthcare.com/health-tech/google-launches-open-health-stack-app-developers-unveils-new-ai-partnerships>.

⁶⁰ *Id.*

⁶¹ Fei Jiang et al., *Artificial Intelligence in Healthcare: Past, Present, and Future*, 2 STROKE AND VASCULAR NEUROLOGY 4 (2017).

Consumers might also turn to general-use AI, like ChatGPT, for information and answers to questions that can have significant impacts on their health.⁶² Consumers already rely on the internet to obtain health information and advice (the “Dr. Google” phenomenon).⁶³ However, unlike the simple retrieval of third-party information that consumers obtain using “Dr. Google,” LLMs actively generate new content, which may be inaccurate or fabricated. Additionally, the level of sophistication and personalization of an LLMs responses might lull a consumer into thinking that the medical information it generates is more reliable than it actually is because “[p]eople tend to more naturally trust something that mimics human behaviors and responses, such as the responses generated by ChatGPT.”⁶⁴ This false sense of reliability is further aggravated by the fact that it is difficult for a consumer to evaluate the accuracy and reliability of the medical information that ChatGPT provides.⁶⁵

There is little doubt that AI-driven health technology will increase in its development, adoption, and sophistication and bring with it many health-related benefits. These benefits are not without risks, however, and AI-driven healthcare presents liability risks when they cause medical injuries.

II. TORT LIABILITY FRAMEWORK FOR BLACK-BOX AI IN HEALTHCARE IN THE US

Currently, tort liability for medical injuries caused by black-box AI could be borne by manufacturers under product liability law and/or by individual and organizational healthcare providers under medical negligence law, which this Part analyzes in the following. It then also considers the burden of proof.

A. MANUFACTURER LIABILITY

Manufacturers of black-box AI can face claims of strict or negligent product liability, though it is unclear whether AI would be considered a

⁶² See Mindy Duffourc and Sara Gerke, *Generative AI in Health Care and Liability Risks for Physicians and Safety Concerns for Patients*, JAMA (Jul. 6, 2023), doi:10.1001/jama.2023.9630.

⁶³ Joanna Burzyńska, et al., *Dr. Google: Physicians—The Web—Patients Triangle: Digital Skills and Attitudes Towards e-Health Solutions Among Physicians in South Eastern Poland—A Cross-Sectional Study in a Pre-COVID-19 Era*, 20 INT’L J. ENV’T RSCH. PUB. HEALTH 2 (2023).

⁶⁴ See *Will ChatGPT Transform Healthcare?*, 29 NATURE MED. 505 (2023).

⁶⁵ See Johnson, *supra* note 49.

“product” subject to product liability law.⁶⁶ There is some support for finding that software is a product because it is considered a “good” under the Uniform Commercial Code and taxed as a good.⁶⁷ Additionally, damage caused by information errors have been subject to product liability.⁶⁸ However, courts do not agree on whether data constitutes “tangible personal property,” a defining characteristic of a “product” under the *Third Restatement*.⁶⁹

Assuming that AI is considered a product, strict product liability would focus on the black-box AI's condition, whereas fault-based product liability focuses on the manufacturer's conduct. However, the legal analysis of strict and negligent product liability claims often overlaps because determining whether a product is defective requires some evaluation of the manufacturer's behavior relating to its design, manufacture, and marketing.⁷⁰ As a result, the general factors governing both strict and negligent product liability claims are similar.⁷¹

A black-box AI manufacturer might be strictly liable if:

- (1) the AI was unreasonably dangerous (defective),
- (2) when it left the manufacturer's control, and
- (3) caused injury.⁷²

Negligent product liability requires the plaintiff has to establish that “the defective condition of the . . . [AI] was the result of negligence.”⁷³ A defective condition can result from at least one of three defects:

- (1) design defect,
- (2) manufacturing defect, and/or

⁶⁶ Michael D. Scott, *Tort Liability for Vendors of Insecure Software: Has the Time Finally Come?*, 67 MD. L. REV. 425, 461-467 (2008).

⁶⁷ *Id.* at 462.

⁶⁸ *Id.* at 465-66.

⁶⁹ *Id.* at 463.

⁷⁰ See *Denny v. Ford Motor Co.*, 662 N.E.2d 730, 735 (N.Y. 1995) (the “risk-utility” test for strict product liability judges “the reasonableness of an actor's conduct . . . in light of a number of situational and policy-driven factors.”).

⁷¹ 96 A.L.R.3d 22 (Originally published in 1979) (negligent and strict liability for design defects requires a similar analysis). In fact, several states have codified product liability law to merge strict and fault-based liability principles. See, e.g., La. Stat. Ann. § 9:2800.52 (West); Miss. Code. Ann. § 11-1-63 (West); Conn. Gen. Stat. Ann. § 52-572m et seq. (West).

⁷² See *Burlington N. & Santa Fe Ry. Co. v. ABC-NACO*, 706, 906 N.E.2d 83, 96 (Ill. App. Ct. 2009); *Dillon v. Zeneca Corp.*, 42 P.3d 598, 603 (Ariz. App. 2002).

⁷³ See *Niemela v. Imperial Mfg., Inc.*, 263 P.3d 1191, 1199 (Utah Ct. App. 2011); *Chestnut v. Ford Motor Co.*, 445 F.2d 967, 968-69 (4th Cir.1971).

(3) marketing defect related to the AI's instructions and warnings.⁷⁴

The following analyzes these three defects and potential defenses of black-box AI manufacturers.

1. DESIGN DEFECTS

Design defects stem from flaws in the design that make a product dangerous for its intended or reasonably foreseeable use.⁷⁵ A black-box AI's design may be defective if it presents an unreasonable danger to the consumer⁷⁶ and/or is not safe for its intended or reasonably foreseeable use.⁷⁷ Parties that partially contribute to the creation of a black-box AI, for example through writing portions of code or supplying a training data set, might be considered component part manufacturers, who can be liable for injuries caused by defectively designed parts that were integrated into a final AI.⁷⁸ However, component part manufacturers can escape such liability if they followed the design specifications of the end-product manufacturer and did not know or had no reason to know that the AI's design was defective.⁷⁹

An unreasonably dangerous black-box AI will subject its manufacturer to liability for injuries it causes.⁸⁰ The Restatement (Second) of Torts describes an unreasonable danger as one that is "beyond that which would be contemplated by the ordinary consumer who purchases it, with the ordinary knowledge common to the community as to its characteristics."⁸¹ The Restatement (Third) of Torts replaces the "consumer expectations" test with a "risk-utility" test, which weighs a product's risks

⁷⁴ See *Brown v. Superior Ct.*, 751 P.2d 470, 475 (Cal. 1988) (noting three types of product defects: manufacturing, design, and instruction and warning); The Restatement (Third) of Torts also recognizes product liability for drugs and medical devices that have manufacturing or design defects or inadequate instructions for warnings. RESTATEMENT (THIRD) OF TORTS: PROD. LIAB. § 6 (AM. L. INST. 1998).

⁷⁵ See *id.* § 2.

⁷⁶ See 96 A.L.R.3d 22, § 3 (Originally published in 1979) (noting several cases, such as from Colorado, Florida, and Indiana).

⁷⁷ See *id.* § 4 (noting several cases, such as from Arizona, Arkansas, and Florida); § 5 (noting cases from California).

⁷⁸ See generally, AM. L. PROD. LIAB. 3d § 8:14.

⁷⁹ See STUART M. SPEISER ET AL., AMERICAN LAW OF TORTS § 18:135. (3d ed. 2018).

⁸⁰ See 54 A.L.R.3d 352 (Originally published in 1973) (noting that in accordance with Section 402A of the Second Restatement of Torts "in most jurisdictions, for the doctrine to apply, the product must not only be in a defective condition, but such condition must be dangerous to a degree described as 'unreasonable.'"). The Restatement (Third) of Tort employs a similar strict product liability for defective drugs and medical devices that are "not reasonably safe." RESTATEMENT (THIRD) OF TORTS: PROD. LIAB § 6 (AM. L. INST. 1998).

⁸¹ RESTATEMENT (SECOND) OF TORTS: § 402A cmt. a (AM. L. INST. 1977).

and benefits to measure whether a product is unreasonably dangerous, including whether there was a reasonably alternative design that existed when the product was placed on the market.⁸² The overwhelming majority of U.S. courts will likely incorporate some risk-utility considerations to determine whether a black-box AI is unreasonably dangerous in design defect claims.⁸³

The following factors can guide the risk-utility analysis: (1) the AI's usefulness; (2) the probability of danger; (3) the avoidability of danger; (4) the state of the art at the time the AI was manufactured; (5) the effect of eliminating danger on the cost or utility of the AI.⁸⁴ Similarly, a negligent design claim would consider, "(1) the extent that the manufacturer could foresee that (...) [the AI] would cause harm; (2) the likelihood of injury; (3) the magnitude of the burden of guarding against it; and (4) the consequences of placing the burden on the defendant."⁸⁵

2. MANUFACTURING DEFECTS

A black-box AI might suffer from a manufacturing defect if flaws in the manufacturing process depart from the intended design.⁸⁶ An AI with a manufacturing defect would be in a "substandard condition," making it more dangerous than anticipated by its design.⁸⁷ Generally, flaws in the manufacturing process can stem from poor construction, poor workmanship, or defective materials.⁸⁸

For black-box AI, this might relate to defects in the manufacturing of physical components of hardware used alongside the AI or it might include a less tangible part of the manufacturing process such as training the AI with data that departs from the originally intended training data.

⁸² See 73 A.L.R.5th 75 (Originally published in 1999) (courts are reluctant to replace the Second Restatement's "consumer expectations" test with the Third Restatement's "risk-utility" test).

⁸³ See *Branham v. Ford Motor Co.*, 701 S.E.2d 5, 14 (S.C. 2010) ("By our count 35 of the 46 states that recognize strict products liability utilize some form of risk-utility analysis in their approach to determine whether a product is defectively designed.").

⁸⁴ See *In re Cook Med., Inc., IVC Filters Mktg., Sales Pracs. & Prod. Liab. Litig.*, 431 F. Supp. 3d 1033, 1047 (S.D. Ind. 2020).

⁸⁵ See *Slisze v. Stanley-Bostitch*, 979 P.2d 317, 320 (Utah 1999).

⁸⁶ See *Am. Tobacco Co. v. Grinnell*, 951 S.W.2d 420, 434 (Tex. 1997); RESTATEMENT (THIRD) OF TORTS: PROD. LIAB § 2 (a) (AM. L. INST. 1998).

⁸⁷ See *Gall v. Smith & Nephew, Inc.*, 286 Cal. Rptr. 3d 108, 114 (Cal. App. 5th 2021); *Longo v. E.I. Dupont De Nemours & Co.*, 632 So. 2d 1193, 1197 (La. Ct. App.), writ denied, 637 So. 2d 464 (La. 1994); *MacPherson v. Buick Motors*, 217 N.Y. 382, 111 N.E. 1050 (1916).

⁸⁸ See *Tears v. Bos. Sci. Corp.*, 344 F. Supp. 3d 500, 510 (S.D.N.Y. 2018).

Manufacturers of component parts of a black-box AI may be liable to the end user if (1) a component part suffered from a manufacturing defect and (2) the part did not undergo a “substantial change” when incorporated into the final AI.⁸⁹ The manifestation of a risk inherent from a black-box AI that was manufactured in accordance with its design specifications is not evidence of a manufacturing defect.⁹⁰

3. MARKETING DEFECTS

A black-box AI manufacturer might be liable for injuries caused by inadequate instructions for the AI's use or inadequate warnings about potential risks of using the AI. Manufacturers usually have a duty to warn consumers of the inherent risks of which they knew or should have known,⁹¹ including risks inherent in the intended use of the product as well as those inherent in reasonably foreseeable misuse.⁹² Foreseeability concerns expectations that are “[o]bjectively reasonable” and not merely possible.⁹³

Black-box AI manufacturers must also conduct post-market monitoring by reviewing “research, adverse reaction reports, scientific literature and other available” data about the AI to ensure that the existing warnings and instructions are sufficient.⁹⁴ Component part manufacturers have a duty to warn the buyers that incorporate that component of inherent risks, but they generally do not have a duty to warn the ultimate consumers about the dangers of the final AI, unless they knew or should have known that the component would become unreasonably dangerous when integrated into the manufacturer's black-box AI design.⁹⁵

⁸⁹ See SPEISER ET AL., *supra* note 79, at § 18:135.

⁹⁰ See Gall, 286 Cal. Rptr. 3d at 114 (finding that the risk of a pseudotumor was “consistent with a perfect implant and is not probative of a defect”).

⁹¹ See Thacker v. Ethicon, Inc., 47 F.4th 451, 459 (6th Cir. 2022).

⁹² See Mack v. Stryker Corp., 748 F.3d 845, 849 (8th Cir. 2014).

⁹³ Winnett v. Winnett, 310 N.E.2d 1, 5 (Ill. 1974) (finding that it was not reasonably foreseeable that a child would approach and put their fingers into a piece of farm equipment while in operation).

⁹⁴ See Rosen v. St. Jude Med., Inc., 41 F. Supp. 3d 170, 184 (N.D.N.Y. 2014); Baker v. St. Agnes Hosp., 70 A.D.2d 400 (N.Y. App. Div. 2d Dept. 1979); McLaughlin v. Bayer Corp., 172 F. Supp. 3d 804, 820 (E.D. Pa. 2016).

⁹⁵ See RESTATEMENT (THIRD) OF TORTS: PROD. LIAB § 5 (AM. L. INST. 1998); Levine v. Wyeth Inc., 684 F.2d 1338, 1346 (M.D. Fla. 2010); Longo v. E.I. Dupont De Nemours & Co., 632 So. 2d 1193, 1197 (La. Ct. App.), writ denied, 637 So. 2d 464 (La. 1994); Westphal v. E.I. du Pont de Nemours & Co., Inc., 531 N.W.2d 386, 365–66 (Ct. App. Wis. 1995). AM. L. PROD. LIAB. 3d § 8:18.

4. DEFENSES

Black-box AI manufacturers can assert a variety of defenses in product liability claims. First, these claims may be preempted under Section 521 of the Federal Food, Drug, and Cosmetic Act (FDCA).⁹⁶ An AI with software functions that relate to “the diagnosis, cure, mitigation, prevention, or treatment of a disease or condition” will likely be considered an AI-based medical device when the healthcare provider is not able to “independently review the basis” for the AI’s output.⁹⁷ However, it may not include some black-box AIs, such as those with functions intended for “maintaining or encouraging a healthy lifestyle.”⁹⁸ Additionally, while manufacturers of AI-based medical devices that underwent the FDA’s premarket approval (PMA) will likely be entitled to preemption, preemption will be unavailable to those that underwent the less rigorous 510(k) process.⁹⁹

Second, black-box AI manufacturers may also avoid strict product liability in design defect claims involving “unavoidably unsafe” AI.¹⁰⁰ An AI may be “unavoidably unsafe” if (1) at the time it was made, “it could not be made safe for its intended use even applying the best available testing and research; and (2) the benefits of the [product] justified its risk.”¹⁰¹ Drugs and medical devices have both been recognized as unavoidably unsafe products that justify an exemption because imposing liability “would be ‘against the public interest’ . . . because of ‘the very serious tendency to stifle medical research and testing.’”¹⁰² Black-box AI used to treat medical conditions or alleviate suffering may receive similar treatment as an “unavoidably unsafe” product, making it possible for manufacturers that sidestep the PMA process to still avoid liability.¹⁰³

Third, black-box AI manufacturers may also avoid product liability if the AI “conformed to the state of the art in existence at the time the [AI]

⁹⁶ See 21 U.S.C. § 360k.

⁹⁷ See *id.* §§ 321h(1); 321j(o)(1)(E).

⁹⁸ See *id.* §§ 321h(1); 321j(o)(1)(B). For more information, see Gerke, *supra* note 26, at 96–121.

⁹⁹ See *Riegel v. Medtronic, Inc.* 552 U.S. 312 (2008) (preemption for devices that receive PMA); *but see Medtronic v. Lohr*, 518 U.S. 470 (1996) (no preemption for device that entered market through 510(k) pathway).

¹⁰⁰ See RESTATEMENT (SECOND) OF TORTS: § 402A cmt. k (AM. L. INST. 1977); *Allen v. G.D. Searle & Co.*, 708 F. Supp. 1142, 1149 (D. Or. 1989) (noting that Oregon and “[m]ost other states have adopted section 402A and its comments”).

¹⁰¹ *Burningham v. Wright Med. Tech., Inc.*, 448 P.3d 1283, 1291 (Utah 2019).

¹⁰² See *Brown*, 751 P.2d at 475 (drugs); *Hufft v. Horowitz*, 5 Cal. Rptr. 2d 377, 384 (Cal. Ct. App. 1992), *modified* (Mar. 17, 1992) (medical devices).

¹⁰³ See *Burningham* 448 P.3d at 1290 (recognizing affirmative defense based on Comment k).

was ... manufactured.”¹⁰⁴ State-of-the-art is usually determined by what is feasible to reflect what reasonably *can be done*, considering factors such as whether a design was practical, technologically and mechanically sound, and in compliance with government regulations.¹⁰⁵ While industry custom, which refers to what *is done* in the industry, can be used to establish the relevant state-of-the-art in the industry, custom itself is not sufficient to prove a state-of-the-art defense.¹⁰⁶

Fourth, black-box AI manufacturers may also avoid liability under the learned intermediary doctrine (LID), which is recognized by many U.S. jurisdictions.¹⁰⁷ The LID would treat the negligence of a healthcare provider as a superseding cause of the injury when the provider knew or should have known that the AI was unreasonably dangerous.¹⁰⁸ Under the LID, manufacturers that properly warn physicians of risks inherent in using the AI would generally not be liable for injuries when such risks materialize.¹⁰⁹

Finally, black-box AI manufacturers may also avoid liability when an injury resulted from a consumer's misuse, alteration, or modification of the AI, or from consumer negligence.¹¹⁰ A consumer misuses a product when they “use the product in direct contravention to the product's warnings and instructions.”¹¹¹ However, the manufacturer would still be liable if the consumer's misuse was reasonably foreseeable at the time the AI was sold.¹¹² Additionally, if the AI was altered or modified after it left the manufacturer's control, the manufacturer would generally not be liable for injuries caused by those alterations or modifications, unless they failed “to warn of the dangers resulting from a foreseeable alteration or modification.”¹¹³ Similarly, manufacturers may not be liable for injuries if

¹⁰⁴ See *Hughes v. Massey-Ferguson, Inc.*, 522 N.W.2d 294, 295 (Iowa 1994); *Potter v. Chicago Pneumatic Tool Co.*, 694 A.2d 1319, 1346 (Conn. 1997) (summarizing the different approaches to state-of-the-art evidence).

¹⁰⁵ See *Hughes*, 522 N.W.2d at 295.

¹⁰⁶ See *id.*

¹⁰⁷ See RESTATEMENT (THIRD) OF TORTS: PROD. LIAB. § 6 cmt. a (AM. L. INST. 1998).

¹⁰⁸ *Glover v. Bausch & Lomb, Inc.*, 275 A.3d 168, 179 (Conn. 2022).

¹⁰⁹ RESTATEMENT (THIRD) OF TORTS: PROD. LIAB. § 6 cmt. a (AM. L. INST. 1998).

¹¹⁰ *Morgen v. Ford Motor Co.*, 797 N.E.2d 1146, 1149 (Ind. 2003); See *Campbell Hausfeld/Scott Fetzer Co. v. Johnson*, 109 N.E.3d 953, 959 (Ind. 2018) (allowing a consumer's misuse to completely bar recovery; *but see* *Mulherin v. Ingersoll-Rand Co.*, 628 P.2d 1301, 1304 (Utah 1981) (applying comparative fault principles to reduce recovery).

¹¹¹ *Campbell*, 109 N.E.3d at 959.

¹¹² *Morgen*, 797 N.E.2d at 1150; *Campbell*, 109 N.E.3d at 959.

¹¹³ See N.C. Gen. Stat. Ann. § 99B-3 (West); *Hines v. Joy Mfg. Co.*, 850 F.2d 1146 (6th Cir. 1988) (no liability for alterations and modifications); *but see* *Witthauer v. Burkhart Roentgen, Inc.*, 467 N.W.2d 439, 445 (N.D. 1991) (liability if failure to warn of foreseeable alternations and modifications).

the user was either contributorily negligent or knowingly assumed the risks that caused their injury.¹¹⁴

B. HEALTHCARE PROVIDER LIABILITY

Individual and organizational healthcare providers that employ black-box AI can be directly liable for a patient's injury caused by their negligence.¹¹⁵ They can also be held vicariously liable for injuries caused by the negligence of a third party acting under their supervision and control.¹¹⁶ However, a black-box AI itself cannot be negligent for its reasoning or output because it is not a legal person held to behavioral standards in tort.¹¹⁷ To recover for an AI-caused injury under a negligence-based tort, a plaintiff must prove that the healthcare provider (1) owed them a duty of care and (2) breached that duty, which (3) caused (4) damages.¹¹⁸ The following analyzes the first three elements of a patient's claim (i.e., duty, breach, and causation) and potential defenses of individual and organizational healthcare providers using black-box AI.

1. DUTY

Individual healthcare providers that use black-box AI to treat patients have a duty to use the "degree of reasonable care and skill expected

¹¹⁴ See *Hadar v. AVCO Corp.*, 886 A.2d 225, 229 (Pa. Super. Ct. 2005) (A consumer assumes a risk when they subjectively "know[] of the specific defect eventually causing his injury and voluntarily proceed[] to use the product with knowledge of the danger caused by the defect."). Compare *Smith v. Ingersoll-Rand Co.*, 14 P.3d 990, 996 (Alaska 2000) (comparative fault allowed in product liability actions) with *Seay v. Chrysler Corp.*, 609 P.2d 1382, 1384 (1980) (comparative negligence not applicable in strict product liability cases), and *Mauch v. Mfr.'s Sales & Serv., Inc.*, 345 N.W.2d 338, 347 (N.D. 1984) (assumption of risk, but not comparative fault, can be a defense in a strict product liability claim).

¹¹⁵ See *Morrison v. MacNamara*, 407 A.2d 555, 560 (D.C. 1979) ("The elements which govern ordinary negligence actions are also applicable in actions for professional negligence."); see *Elam v. Coll. Park Hosp.*, 132 Cal. App. 3d 332, 338 (Cal. Ct. App. 1982) (discussing the elements of a medical malpractice claim in the U.S.); 3 Summary Pa. Juris. 2d *Torts* § 37:45 (2d ed.), Westlaw (database updated July 2018) (discussing theories of direct hospital liability).

¹¹⁶ See W.R. Habeeb, Annotation, *Liability of One Physician or Surgeon for Malpractice of Another*, 85 A.L.R. 2d 889 § 4 (1962) (regarding vicarious liability for physicians); Cassandra P. Priestley, *Hospital Liability for the Negligence of Independent Contractors: A Summary of Trends*, 50 J. Mo. B. 263, 264 (1994) (regarding vicarious liability for hospitals).

¹¹⁷ See Duffourc, *supra* note 17.

¹¹⁸ See cases cited, *supra* note 115.

of members of the medical profession under the same or similar circumstances,”¹¹⁹ taking into account the provider’s training and specialization.¹²⁰ Organizational healthcare providers also owe a direct duty of care to patients to be reasonable in their use of black-box AI, including in the selection, implementation, and maintenance of the AI, training, and oversight of employees that use AI, and the implementation of protocols and procedures associated with using AI.¹²¹

2. BREACH

Individual healthcare providers are negligent when they breach the applicable standard of care by failing to “exercise the amount of care, skill, and diligence exercised generally in the community by doctors engaged in the same field.”¹²² The standard of care is flexible and can “depend[] on many factors, including a doctor’s specialty, the resources available, and the advances of the medical profession at the time of the alleged negligent act.”¹²³ Complicating the landscape for new medical technologies, including AI, is the fact that there is not always a single course of action required by the standard of care.¹²⁴ As a result, individual providers that use black-box AI to treat patients will generally not be negligent as long as their medical treatment is supported by “a considerable number of his professional brethren in good standing in his community.”¹²⁵

3. CAUSATION

If a healthcare provider who uses black-box AI to treat a patient breaches the standard of care, this breach will sufficiently cause a patient injury when it is both a cause-in-fact and legal (or “proximate”) cause of the injury.¹²⁶ The provider’s breach will be a cause-in-fact when “but for” the breach, the patient would not have suffered an injury.¹²⁷ Courts use different

¹¹⁹ See *Dingle v. Belin*, 749 A.2d 157, 164 (Md. 2000).

¹²⁰ See *Betesh v. United States*, 400 F. Supp. 238, 247 (D.D.C. 1974) (for physicians); *Berdyck v. Shinde*, 613 N.E.2d 1014, 1017 (Ohio 1993) (for nurse practitioners).

¹²¹ See *Darling v. Charleston Cmty. Mem’l Hosp.*, 211 N.E.2d 253 (Ill. 1965); See generally *Adelman & Robertson*; 3 Summary Pa. Juris. 2d *Torts* § 37:45 (2d ed.), WESTLAW (database updated July 2018) (discussing theories of direct hospital liability).

¹²² *Betesh*, 400 F. Supp. at 247.

¹²³ *Heinrich v. Sweet*, 308 F.3d 48, 63 (1st Cir. 2002).

¹²⁴ *Duckworth v. Bennett*, 181 A. 558, 559 (Pa. 1935).

¹²⁵ *Id.*

¹²⁶ See *Ploch v. Hamai*, 213 S.W.3d 135, 141 (Mo. Ct. App. 2006).

¹²⁷ See JAMES UNDERWOOD, *TORT LAW: PRINCIPLES IN PRACTICE* 227-255 (3rd ed., Wolters Kluwer, 2022) 227-255 (discussing alternatives to but-for test).

tests for proximate cause.¹²⁸ Under the foreseeability test that the majority of courts apply, for a healthcare provider's breach to be a proximate cause of the patient's injury, the injury suffered must have been a foreseeable result of the provider's breach.¹²⁹

4. DEFENSES

Healthcare providers using black-box AI to treat patients may assert affirmative defenses of contributory and comparative fault, which can reduce or eliminate the defendant's liability when the plaintiff's or another party's negligence caused or contributed to the plaintiff's injury.¹³⁰ Whether and how much a defendant healthcare provider's liability might be reduced by the fault of another party depends on each state's approach to contributory and comparative negligence doctrines.¹³¹

For example, a patient who provides incorrect information might be negligent if the provider used a black-box AI that relied on this information to produce a treatment recommendation that the provider later relied upon. Additionally, a third-party AI developer might be negligent if they provided incorrect instructions regarding the use of the black-box AI, and the provider relied on those instructions to make a recommendation.

C. PROOF CONSIDERATIONS

As a general rule, plaintiffs bear the initial burden of proof.¹³² In cases involving black-box AI, this burden can be met in most jurisdictions using the preponderance of the evidence, "reasonable degree of medical certainty," or "reasonable degree of medical probability" standard to show that a duty was breached and caused damage.¹³³ However, a few

¹²⁸ See *id.* at 255-290 (discussing direct cause, the substantial factor, and the foreseeability tests).

¹²⁹ See *id.* at 250.

¹³⁰ See SPEISER ET AL., *supra* note 79, at §§ 7:16, 13:2 (3d ed. 2018) (outlining affirmative defenses of contributory and comparative fault).

¹³¹ See UNDERWOOD, *supra* note 127, at 250, 450; Bloomberg Law, *Understanding Contributory Negligence and Apportionment of Fault* (Feb. 13, 2023), <https://pro.bloomberglaw.com/brief/contributory-negligence-and-apportionment-of-fault/> (discussing the different approaches to contributory and comparative fault).

¹³² See *Physicians, Surgeons, Etc.*, 61 Am. Jur. 2d § 309 (2d ed), Westlaw (database updated Nov. 2021);

¹³³ See *James v. McHenry*, 828 So. 2d 94, 95 (La. App. 2 Cir. 2002) (preponderance of evidence); *Hoffman v. Carter*, 215, 648 S.E.2d 318, 326 (Va. Ct. App. 2007) (reasonable degree of medical certainty is the same as the preponderance of evidence); *Ashland Hosp.*

jurisdictions impose a stricter interpretation of the “reasonable degree of medical certainty” standard to require proof that exceeds a probability.¹³⁴

The majority of U.S. courts will ease the plaintiff’s burden of proving the breach of a duty in cases that justify the application of the doctrine of *res ipsa loquitur*.¹³⁵ In cases involving black-box AI, *res ipsa loquitur* would allow the jury (or judge in a bench trial) to infer negligence when (1) the black-box AI that caused the injury is in exclusive control of the healthcare provider, (2) the kind of injury typically does not occur in the absence of negligence, (3) injured patient was not contributorily negligent, and (4) the healthcare provider is in a superior position to explain the accident.¹³⁶ Additionally, in cases when the defendant healthcare provider violated a statute or other regulation that was intended to protect the plaintiff against the type of injury caused by the black-box AI, the plaintiff might benefit from a stronger rebuttable presumption of negligence under the “negligence per se” doctrine.¹³⁷

III. LIABILITY FRAMEWORK FOR BLACK-BOX AI IN HEALTHCARE IN THE EU

The EU liability framework is grappling with similar issues raised by black-box AI in healthcare as the US. This Part first carves out general principles governing liability for AI-caused medical injuries in the EU. It then examines recent developments in the EU’s approach to liability for AI-caused injuries. Lastly, it compares the EU and US frameworks governing liability for manufacturers and individual and organizational healthcare providers.

A. GENERAL PRINCIPLES GOVERNING LIABILITY FOR AI-CAUSED MEDICAL INJURIES IN THE EU

In the EU, liability for medical injuries is governed under a combination of EU-level law and Member States’ national liability law. The

Corp., 581 S.W.3d at 577–78 (“reasonable degree of medical probability” cannot be “contingent, speculative, or merely possible”).

¹³⁴ See Griffin v. Univ. of Pittsburgh Med. Ctr.-Braddock Hosp., 950 A.2d 996, 1000 (Pa. 2008) (noting that reasonable degree of medical certainty standard is not met by an expert opinion rendered in “more likely than not” terms).

¹³⁵ See Sides v. St. Anthony’s Medical Center, 258 S.W.3d 811, 816-18 (Mo. 2008) (recognizing that all but four states allow the doctrine of *res ipsa loquitur* in medical malpractice cases); La. Stat. Ann. § 9:2794 (West) (*res ipsa loquitur* will shift the burden of proof in Louisiana).

¹³⁶ Karyn K. Ablin, *Res Ipsa Loquitur and Expert Opinion Evidence in Medical Malpractice Cases: Strange Bedfellows*, 82(2) Va. L. Rev. 325 (1996).

¹³⁷ See Stachowski v. Est. of Radman, 95 N.E.3d 542 (Ind. Ct. App. 2018).

EU institutions can enact legal acts, for example in the form of Regulations and Directives, only to the extent that they are authorized to do so under the Treaty on European Union (TEU) and the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU).¹³⁸ Regulations are directly applicable in the 27 EU Member States.¹³⁹ Directives, on the other hand, must first be transposed into Member States' national law.¹⁴⁰ As a result, references in this Article to provisions in EU Directives (or proposed Directives) refer more specifically to those provisions as transposed into Member States' national law either. Additionally, while we cannot provide an overview of each Member State's national strict and fault-based liability laws, we provide some overarching principles that govern liability for medical injuries in the EU. The following first examines manufacturer liability and individual and organizational healthcare provider liability for black-box AI in healthcare under the current EU liability framework. It then also considers the burden of proof.

1. MANUFACTURER LIABILITY

Black-box AI manufacturers in the EU can be liable under strict and/or fault-based product liability.¹⁴¹ Strict product liability, governed by the Product Liability Directive (PLD) as transposed into Member States' national law, imposes liability on manufacturers, including manufacturer of component parts, for injuries caused by their defective products.¹⁴² However, the current PLD applies to “movables” and thus, according to the majority view, would encompass an “intangible” product like black-box AI software only if it was embedded in a tangible product.¹⁴³ For such products, the PLD would rely on consumer expectations of safety to

¹³⁸ See Udo Bux & Mariusz Maciejewski, *Sources and Scope of European Union Law*, EUR. PARL. (April 2023), <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/factsheets/en/sheet/6/sources-and-scope-of-european-union-law>; Consolidated Version of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union art. 267, Oct. 26, 2012, 2012 O.J. (C 326) 47 [hereinafter TFEU].

¹³⁹ TFEU art. 288(2).

¹⁴⁰ *Id.* art. 288(3).

¹⁴¹ Rod Freeman, et al., *Product Liability and Safety in the EU: Overview*, THOMAS REUTERS PRACTICAL LAW (Aug. 1, 2023), [https://uk.practicallaw.thomsonreuters.com/w-013-0379?transitionType=Default&contextData=\(sc.Default\)&firstPage=true](https://uk.practicallaw.thomsonreuters.com/w-013-0379?transitionType=Default&contextData=(sc.Default)&firstPage=true).

¹⁴² Product Liability Directive (PLD), Council Directive of 25 July 1985 on the Approximation of the Laws, Regulations and Administrative Provisions of the Member States Concerning Liability for Defective Products (85/374/EEC), art. 3, 1985 O.J. (L 210) 29 [hereinafter PLD].

¹⁴³ CHRISTIANE WENDEHORST & YANNIC DULLER, *Safety- and Liability-Related Aspects of Software*, in *CIVIL LIABILITY FOR ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND SOFTWARE* 268–69 (Mark A. Geistfeld, et al. eds., 2023); PLD art. 2.

determine defectiveness by considering (a) the AI's presentation, (b) its reasonably foreseeable use, and (c) the moment in time when the manufacturer put the product on the market.¹⁴⁴ The Court of Justice of the European Union has found that for medical devices marketed for use by vulnerable patients, consumer expectations of safety are "particularly high" and that manufacturers can be liable for injuries caused by such products that are merely "potentially defective."¹⁴⁵ Additionally, Courts in Member States might also include risk-utility considerations, particularly whether or not there was a "reasonable alternative design," when determining whether a black-box AI is defective under the PLD's principles.¹⁴⁶

The current PLD provides for several defenses to strict product liability claims. First, even if a black-box medical system is considered a defective product at the time of the alleged injury, the manufacturer might avoid liability by proving that the defect did not exist at the time the product was placed on the market.¹⁴⁷ Second, the manufacturer might avoid liability if they did not intend for the black-box system to be sold or distributed for "economic purpose."¹⁴⁸ Third, if the defect was a result of the manufacturer's compliance with mandatory regulations applicable to the black-box system, they would not be liable under the current PLD.¹⁴⁹ Fourth, according to the "development risk" or "state-of-the-art" defense, the manufacturer might escape liability for a defective black-box AI in cases where "the state of scientific and technical knowledge at the time when he put the product into circulation was not such as to enable the existence of the defect to be discovered."¹⁵⁰ Notably, while the PLD allows the Member States to exclude the development risk/state-of-the-art as an available defense, most have adopted this defense at least partially.¹⁵¹ Finally, a component part manufacturer can escape liability by proving that the defect was caused by either the defective design of the finished black-box system

¹⁴⁴ PLD art. 6(1).

¹⁴⁵ C-503/13, *Boston Scientific Medizintechnik GmbH v. AOK Sachsen-Anhalt*, ECLI:EU:C:2015:148 (2015), para. 39; See Giorgio Rizzo, *Product Liability and Protection of EU Consumers: Is It Time for a Serious Reassessment?*, 15 J. PRIV. INT'L L. 210, 223 (2019).

¹⁴⁶ WENDEHORST & DULLER, *supra* note 143, at 273 (citing PLD art. 2).

¹⁴⁷ PLD art. 7(b).

¹⁴⁸ *Id.* art. 7(c).

¹⁴⁹ *Id.* art. 7(d).

¹⁵⁰ *Id.* art. 7(e).

¹⁵¹ See *id.* art. 15(b); Fondazione Rosselli, *Analysis of the Economic Impact of the Development Risk Clause as provided by Directive 85/374/EEC on Liability for Defective Products*, https://www.biiicl.org/files/100_rosselli_report.pdf (last visited Jul. 16, 2023) (reporting that all but two Member States - Finland and Luxembourg - have at least partially adopted the development risk defense).

or the instructions provided by the manufacturer of the finished black-box system.¹⁵²

Fault-based product liability is governed by Member States' general fault-based liability law and is not precluded by the PLD.¹⁵³ The core common elements of a tort claim are (1) fault, (2) causation, and (3) damage.¹⁵⁴ A black-box AI manufacturer's fault will be judged objectively based on the position of a reasonable person under the circumstances.¹⁵⁵ If a manufacturer violates a regulation designed to protect against the risk of an AI-caused injury, this violation will weigh in favor of finding that the manufacturer's behavior was unreasonable under the circumstances. As a result, black-box AI manufacturers will likely be liable if they were unreasonable in their design, manufacture, instructions, warning, and monitoring the AI that caused an injury.

2. HEALTHCARE PROVIDER LIABILITY

Tort liability for medical injuries caused by healthcare providers is governed by fault-based principles in all EU Member States.¹⁵⁶ As a result, when the fault of an individual healthcare provider causes patient damage, the provider will be liable under Member States' fault-based tort law. Organizational healthcare providers like hospitals can be vicariously liable for the fault of the individual healthcare providers in their employment, but they can also be directly liable for faults related to personnel, equipment, or facilities.¹⁵⁷

Individual healthcare providers that use black-box AI to treat patients are at fault if they fail to fulfill the objective standard of care in their corresponding field or *lex artis*.¹⁵⁸ This standard of care takes into account the state of medical science at the time of the treatment.¹⁵⁹ As a result, the standard of care for individual healthcare providers that use

¹⁵² PLD art. 7(f).

¹⁵³ Sylvie Gallage-Alwis, *Product Liability and Safety in France: Overview*, THOMAS REUTERS PRACTICAL LAW (Jun. 1, 2022), [https://uk.practicallaw.thomsonreuters.com/w-012-7018?transitionType=Default&contextData=\(sc.Default\)](https://uk.practicallaw.thomsonreuters.com/w-012-7018?transitionType=Default&contextData=(sc.Default)).

¹⁵⁴ BERNHARD A KOCH, *Medical Liability in Europe: Comparative Analysis*, in MEDICAL LIABILITY IN EUROPE 626–39 (Koch ed., 2011).

¹⁵⁵ MARK GEISTFELD, ERNST KARNER, & BERNHARD A KOCH, *Comparative Law Study on Civil Liability for Artificial Intelligence*, in CIVIL LIABILITY FOR ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND SOFTWARE 46–47 (Mark A. Geistfeld, et al. eds., 2023).

¹⁵⁶ *Id.* at 44 (“All European legal systems recognize (tortious) fault-based liability”).

¹⁵⁷ See KOCH, *supra* note 154, at 630 (noting that in addition to vicarious liability, hospitals can also be directly liable for organizational fault).

¹⁵⁸ *Id.* at 628.

¹⁵⁹ *Id.* at 629.

black-box AI might consider the providers' limited ability to predict and understand the AI's output.¹⁶⁰ Healthcare organizations that use black-box AI might also be directly liable for injuries that stem from organizational deficiencies.¹⁶¹ Finally, whether an individual or organizational healthcare provider is at fault in a given case involving a black-box AI will likely be impacted by legislative safety provisions¹⁶² and medical professional rules or guidelines.¹⁶³

A medical injury involving an individual or organizational healthcare provider's use of a black-box AI must be caused by the provider's fault for liability to attach.¹⁶⁴ Factual causation is satisfied when a healthcare provider's breach of the standard of care is a "*condicio sine qua non*" (or but-for cause) of the patient's injury.¹⁶⁵ However, even if the but-for test cannot clearly establish causation in a case involving a black-box AI, some Member States may still impose liability if the healthcare provider's fault increases the risk of the injury that occurred or results in a loss of a chance for the patient to avoid the injury that occurred.¹⁶⁶ On the other hand, a healthcare provider's breach of the standard of care might not be considered a legal cause of the patient's injury if it does not bear a sufficient level of "blameworthiness."¹⁶⁷ Generally, the provider will be

¹⁶⁰ GEISTFELD, KARNER, & KOCH, *supra* note 155, at 56–57.

¹⁶¹ See Koch, *supra* note 154 at 630; See DIETER GIESEN, *International Medical Malpractice Law: A Comparative Law Study of Civil Liability Arising from Medical Care 58-59* (1988) (discussing direct hospital liability).

¹⁶² GEISTFELD, KARNER, & KOCH, *supra* note 155, at 55.

¹⁶³ Koch, *supra* note 154, at 625.

¹⁶⁴ *Id.* at 26.

¹⁶⁵ See GIESEN, *supra* note 161, at 177. A factual causation test that eliminates the healthcare provider's fault from the events surrounding the injury to determine whether the injury would have occurred may have other names. See HERMAN NYS, *Medical Liability in Belgium*, in *MEDICAL LIABILITY IN EUROPE 73-74* (Koch ed., 2011) (Belgium's "theory of equivalence"); BASIL S. MARKESINIS, ET AL., *THE GERMAN LAW OF TORTS: A COMPARATIVE TREATISE 61* (5th ed. 2019) (Germany's method of elimination).

¹⁶⁶ See e.g. ATTILA MENYHARD, *Medical Liability in Hungary*, in *MEDICAL LIABILITY IN EUROPE 301* (Koch ed., 2011) (Hungary's approach to causation and liability for increasing risk of injury); IVO GIESEN & ESTHER ENGELHARD, *Medical Liability in the Netherlands*, in *MEDICAL LIABILITY IN EUROPE 377* (Koch ed., 2011) (shifting the burden of proving causation in the Netherlands in cases of increased risks of damage); NYS, *supra* note 165, at 74 (Belgium provides liability for some causes in which cause-in-fact cannot be established by recognizing a claim for loss of chance); KOCH, *supra* note 154, at 636 (noting that some jurisdictions in Europe eliminate causation issues by recognizing loss of chance as a "distinct damage").

¹⁶⁷ See KOCH, *supra* note 154, at 628 (noting that causation considers both the factual link between the breach to the damage as well as the "blameworthiness" of the conduct.); MIGUEL MARTIN-CASALS & JOSEP SOLE, *Medical Liability in the Spain* in *MEDICAL*

liable if the patient's injury is considered a "natural consequence" of their breach.¹⁶⁸ In some EU Member States, this will be the case even if the injury is considered to be "a highly improbable consequence," while others might exclude liability for injuries that are "extraordinarily unlikely" from the perspective of a healthcare provider with relevant expertise immediately prior to the breach in question.¹⁶⁹

In medical malpractice cases involving black-box AI, there may be multiple causes of a patient's injury. In the majority of EU Member States, when more than one individual or organizational healthcare provider has breached the standard, and those breaches are potential alternative causes of the patient's injury, the providers will be jointly and severally liable.¹⁷⁰ However, in cases where the black-box AI (or some other circumstance like a pre-existing condition) rather than a second healthcare provider is deemed one potential cause of the patient's injury, the healthcare provider may (1) completely escape liability or be liable for the entire damage under an "all-or-nothing" rule; or (2) be apportioned a percentage of the damage under a "proportional liability" rule.¹⁷¹

3. PROOF CONSIDERATIONS

Under the default position, the patient will bear the burden of proof in cases involving injuries caused by black-box AI.¹⁷² The standard of proof in many, but not all, Member States requires more than a preponderance of the evidence.¹⁷³ However, there are several situations in which the plaintiff's burden of proof is either relaxed or shifts completely to the defendant.¹⁷⁴ For example, the burden of proof on negligence or causation

LIABILITY IN EUROPE 468-69 (Koch ed., 2011) (legal causation in Spain considers whether the injury is a "natural, adequate, and sufficient consequence" of the breach).

¹⁶⁸ Compare GIESEN & ENGELHARD, *supra* note 166, at 379–80 (legal causation found by Dutch court even though damage was a highly "improbable consequence) with MARTIN-CASALS & SOLE, *supra* note 167, at 469 (no legal causation in Spain when injury is "extraordinarily unlikely").

¹⁶⁹ See GIESEN & ENGELHARD, *supra* note 166, at 375 (legal causation in the Netherlands considers nature of liability and type of harm).

¹⁷⁰ See KOCH, *supra* note 154, at 635.

¹⁷¹ See *id.* (discussing the different approaches to causation in cases where at least one provider breached the standard of care, but another cause contributed to the damage).

¹⁷² See MENYHARD, *supra* note 166, at 300 (once a plaintiff proves damages and causation in Hungary, fault is presumed).

¹⁷³ See KOCH, *supra* note 154, at 632 (Italy and Sweden require probability, Austria and Poland require high probability, Belgium, France, Czech Republic, and Spain require sometime close to certainty).

¹⁷⁴ *Id.* at 633–34 (discussing presumption and burden shifting mechanisms in several EU Member States).

might shift to the defendant if the black-box AI that caused the injury is deemed to be in the defendant's sphere of control if the defendant is in a better position than the patient to bear the burden of proof, or in the case of "gross errors."¹⁷⁵

B. RECENT DEVELOPMENTS IN THE EU'S APPROACH TO LIABILITY FOR AI-CAUSED INJURIES

With regard to liability for AI-caused injuries, the EU has recognized that an AI's autonomous behavior, data dependency, opacity, lack of interpretability, product and system complexity, continuous adaptation and software updates, and lack of predictability, present liability challenges.¹⁷⁶ As a result, it can be difficult to connect potentially problematic AI decisions made to a legally responsible party, making it difficult for injured persons to obtain compensation under the current liability framework.¹⁷⁷ The newly proposed Product Liability Directive (PLD) and proposed AI Liability Directive (AILD) represent the EC's recent attempt to present a more harmonized solution to these liability challenges.¹⁷⁸ An overarching goal of the two newly proposed Directives is to govern risks presented in the digital age in a manner that balances the interests of beneficial innovation with the rights of injured parties.¹⁷⁹ The proposed PLD attempts to do this by, "ensuring a fair balance between the legitimate interests of manufacturers, injured persons and consumers in general."¹⁸⁰ The proposed AILD seeks to do this by simultaneously ensuring compensation for AI-caused damage and providing certainty surrounding liability for risks associated with AI.¹⁸¹ The following first analyzes product

¹⁷⁵ See MENYHARD, *supra* note 166, at 337 (Hungary); BGB § 630h (Germany).

¹⁷⁶ *Report From the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council and the Economic and Social Committee on the Safety and Liability Implications of Artificial Intelligence, the Internet of Things and Robotics*, COM(2020) 64 final (Feb. 19, 2020); *Commission Staff Working Document Impact Assessment Report Accompanying the Document Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on Adapting Non-Contractual Civil Liability Rules to Artificial Intelligence*, COM(2022) 496 final (Sept. 28, 2022).

¹⁷⁷ Commission White Paper On Artificial Intelligence - A European Approach to Excellence and Trust, COM(2020) 65 final (Feb. 19, 2020).

¹⁷⁸ See generally proposed PLD and proposed AILD.

¹⁷⁹ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and the Council Laying Down Harmonized Rules on Artificial Intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and Amending Certain Union Legislative Acts, Explanatory Memorandum, COM(2021) 206 final (Apr. 21, 2021) [hereinafter proposed AI Act]; proposed AILD, Explanatory Memorandum.

¹⁸⁰ Proposed PLD, Explanatory Memorandum.

¹⁸¹ Proposed AILD, Explanatory Memorandum.

liability under the proposed PLD and then fault-based liability under the proposed AILD.

1. PRODUCT LIABILITY UNDER THE PROPOSED EU PRODUCT LIABILITY DIRECTIVE

The proposed PLD retains the main structure for EU-level product liability by providing for strict liability when defective products cause damage.¹⁸² Member States' national laws governing strict product liability cannot be more or less restrictive than those set forth in the proposed PLD.¹⁸³ The proposed PLD explicitly includes software in its "product" definition.¹⁸⁴ Under the proposed PLD, a product is defective if it "does not provide the safety which the public at large is entitled to expect, taking all circumstances into account."¹⁸⁵ While similar to the current PLD's "consumer expectations" test, the proposed PLD adds new factors that might affect defectiveness, including, but are not limited to (a) the product's presentation and instructions, (b) the product's "reasonably foreseeable use and misuse," (c) the product's ability to continually learn, (d) the product's effect on other products with which it is reasonably expected to be used, (e) the time when the manufacturer places the product on the market or loses control over the product, (f) "product safety requirements," (g) regulatory intervention related to the product's safety, and (h) expectations of the intended consumers.¹⁸⁶ The term "manufacturer's control" includes post-market software updates, upgrades, and modifications.¹⁸⁷

New evidentiary rules in the proposed PLD will make it more difficult for an AI manufacturer to avoid liability. First, the proposed PLD provides a mechanism for injured parties with plausible claims to obtain evidence from defendants, thus alleviating the information asymmetry that victims may encounter in cases involving black-box AI.¹⁸⁸ Second, the PLD provides for a presumption of defectiveness and/or causation when the claimant faces "excessive difficulties" in proving one or both of these elements "due to technical or scientific complexity" of a product that likely

¹⁸² *See generally* proposed PLD.

¹⁸³ *Id.* art. 3.

¹⁸⁴ *Id.* art. 4(1).

¹⁸⁵ *Id.* art. 6(1).

¹⁸⁶ *Id.*

¹⁸⁷ *Id.* art. 4(5).

¹⁸⁸ *Id.* art. 8(1). However, when the disclosure of such evidence would reveal trade secrets, the court ordering the disclosure can offer the requisite confidentiality protection. *Id.* art. 8(4).

contained a damage-causing defect.¹⁸⁹ A patient injured by a black-box AI would be entitled to a presumption of defectiveness if the manufacturer failed to either disclose required evidence, failed to comply with a safety standard, or if their injury was caused by an “obvious malfunction” in the normal course of the AI’s use.¹⁹⁰ Additionally, a presumption of causation would apply if the injury constitutes damage “of a kind typically consistent” with the defect.¹⁹¹

A manufacturer may not be liable under the proposed PLD if they “did not place the product on the market or put it into service.”¹⁹² Additionally, a manufacturer may not be liable if it is probable that the product was not defective when they placed it on the market or when the manufacturer could not have discovered the defect considering the “objective state of scientific and technical knowledge” at that time.¹⁹³ However, a party that subsequently substantially modifies a product will be considered a “manufacturer” and will be strictly liable for injuries caused by the modification.¹⁹⁴

2. FAULT-BASED LIABILITY UNDER THE PROPOSED AI LIABILITY DIRECTIVE

The proposed AILD provides fault-based liability rules for AI-caused damages that are unrelated to defective products.¹⁹⁵ Unlike the proposed PLD, the proposed AILD does not prohibit Member States from imposing fault-based liability laws that are stricter than those contained in the newly proposed Directive.¹⁹⁶ The proposed AILD relies on the substantive duties of care already established by the EU Member States’ national law. A determination of fault is still based on non-compliance with an existing “duty of care under Union or national law.”¹⁹⁷ The proposed AILD defines “duty of care” as “a required standard of conduct, set by national or Union law, in order to avoid damage to legal interests recognized at national or Union law level, including life, physical integrity, property and the protection of fundamental rights.”¹⁹⁸ Finally, injuries caused by a

¹⁸⁹ Proposed PLD art. 9(4).

¹⁹⁰ *See id.* art. 9(2).

¹⁹¹ *See id.* art. 9(3).

¹⁹² *Id.* art. 10(a).

¹⁹³ *Id.* art. 10(1)(c), (e).

¹⁹⁴ *Id.* art. 7(4); 10(1)(g).

¹⁹⁵ Proposed AILD, Explanatory Memorandum.

¹⁹⁶ *Id.* art. 1(4), Recital (11).

¹⁹⁷ *See id.*, Explanatory Memorandum, Recital (23).

¹⁹⁸ *Id.* art. 2(9).

breach of a duty of care that occurs subsequent to an AI's output appear to fall outside of the AILD's scope.¹⁹⁹

The AILD seeks to decrease the evidentiary burden on plaintiffs by enabling Member State courts to order defendants and third parties to produce evidence that the court determines is "necessary and proportionate" to a claim for damage caused by a high-risk AI system.²⁰⁰ The AILD defines a "high-risk AI system" by referring to the AI Act.²⁰¹ Under the AI Act, black-box medical AI will qualify as a high-risk system because it will require "third-party conformity assessment" prior to market authorization²⁰² as either a class IIa, IIb, or III "medical device" under the Medical Device Regulation (MDR)²⁰³ or as a class B, C or D "in vitro diagnostic medical device" under the In Vitro Diagnostic Medical Device Regulation (IVDR).²⁰⁴ Failure to comply with an order to produce evidence can result in a rebuttable presumption of fault for the party on the matter which the evidence was intended to prove.²⁰⁵

Finally, the AILD provides for a rebuttable presumption that a defendant's fault caused the AI's injury-causing output or lack thereof.²⁰⁶ This presumption applies when (1) the fault is "reasonably likely" to have "influenced" the AI's output, and (2) the "output gave rise to the damage."²⁰⁷ Because fault must influence the AI's output, the AILD does not apply, and thus does not provide a presumption of causation when human fault follows, rather than precedes, the AI output because in that case, the "output is not interposed between the human act or omission and the damage."²⁰⁸

¹⁹⁹ See *id.* Recital (15); Mindy Duffourc & Sara Gerke, *The Proposed EU Directives for AI Liability Leave Worrying Gaps Likely to Impact Medical AI*, 6 NPJ DIGITAL MED. 77 (2023).

²⁰⁰ Proposed AILD art. 3(4).

²⁰¹ *Id.* art. 2(2).

²⁰² Proposed AI Act, art. 6(1), (2), Annex II (11)–(12).

²⁰³ Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on Medical Devices, Amending Directive 2001/83/EC, Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 and Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 and Repealing Council Directives 90/385/EEC and 93/42/EEC, art. 2(1), (4), annex VIII 2.5, 3.5, 3.7, 6.2–6.3, 2017 O.J. (L 117) 1 [hereinafter MDR].

²⁰⁴ Regulation (EU) 2017/746 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on in Vitro Diagnostic Medical Devices and Repealing Directive 98/79/EC and Commission Decision 2010/227/EU, art. 2(2), annex VIII, 2017 O.J. (L 117) 176 [hereinafter IVDR].

²⁰⁵ Proposed AILD art. 3(5).

²⁰⁶ *Id.* art. 4(1).

²⁰⁷ *Id.*

²⁰⁸ See *id.*; AILD recital 15.

C. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE EU AND US LIABILITY FRAMEWORKS

Despite the various approaches in EU Member States, there is some concordance on the basic liability rules that govern medical injuries between both the EU Member States themselves and the approach in the US. The two tables below compare the current EU and US frameworks governing liability for black-box AI manufacturers (Table 1) and individual and organizational healthcare providers using black-box AI (Table 2). The yellow highlights in both tables indicate areas of law in EU Member States that will be affected by the proposed PLD and AILD.

Tort Liability for Manufacturers	US		EU	
	Strict Product	Fault-Based	Strict Product	Fault-Based
Level of Substantive Governing Law	Primarily State	Primarily State	Primarily EU (through PLD as transposed into Member State Law)	Member State
Elements of Liability	Product defect, causation, and damages	Manufacturer negligence, causation, and damages	Product defect, causation, and damages	Manufacturer negligence, causation, and damages
Types of Product Defects	Design, manufacturing, and marketing	N/A	Design, manufacturing, and marketing	N/A
Types of Manufacturer Negligence	N/A	Negligent design, manufacturing, and marketing	N/A	Negligent design, manufacturing, and marketing
Legal Standard for Determining Product Design Defects	Consumer expectations and/or risk-utility	N/A	Consumer expectations and/or risk-utility	N/A

Legal Standard for Determining Whether a Manufacturer Is Negligent	N/A	Breach of a duty of care	N/A	Breach of a duty of care
Liability for Manufacturers of Component Parts	<p>Defective design, manufacturing, marketing of component parts.</p> <p>No <i>design defect</i> liability if designed to manufacturer's specification and had no actual or constructive knowledge of design defect.</p> <p>No <i>manufacturing defect</i> liability if component part underwent substantial change when incorporated into final product.</p> <p>No <i>marketing defect</i> liability for failing to warn end user if no actual or constructive knowledge that component part</p>	Negligent design, manufacturing, and marketing of component parts	<p>Defective design, manufacturing, marketing of component parts.</p> <p>No liability if defect was caused by <i>design or instructions</i> of final product.</p>	Negligent design, manufacturing, and marketing of component parts

	would make product unreasonably dangerous.			
Defenses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preemption • Unavoidably unsafe product • State-of-the-art • Learned Intermediary Doctrine • Consumer misuse, alteration, or modification • Consumer negligence • Assumption of risk 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preemption • Unavoidably unsafe product • State-of-the-art • Learned Intermediary Doctrine • Consumer misuse, alteration, or modification • Consumer negligence • Assumption of risk 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No defect on market entry • No intention to sell or distribute for economic purpose • Defect caused by compliance with mandatory regulations • Development risk/state-of-the-art 	Varies with Member State law

TABLE 1: TORT LIABILITY FOR BLACK-BOX AI MANUFACTURERS IN THE US AND EU

Medical Liability for Healthcare Providers	US	EU
Type of Liability	Fault-based (primarily tort)	Fault-based (primarily contract)
Level of Substantive Governing Law	State	Member State
Elements of Liability	Duty, breach, causation, damage	Fault, causation, damage
Standard of Proof	Probability	Generally more than probability
Burden of Proof	Plaintiff	Plaintiff

Deviations from General Burden of Proof Rules	Relaxation of plaintiff's burden of proof on negligence under <i>res ipsa loquitur</i> and negligence <i>per se</i> doctrines.	Relaxation of plaintiff's burden of proof on negligence and causation in various circumstances.
Legal Standard for Determining Whether a Healthcare Provider is at Fault	The level of care exercised by medical providers in the same field.	The level of care owed by medical providers in the same field.
Types of Healthcare Providers	Individual, organizational	Individual, organizational

TABLE 2: MEDICAL LIABILITY FOR INDIVIDUAL AND ORGANIZATIONAL HEALTHCARE PROVIDERS USING BLACK-BOX AI IN THE US AND EU

IV. LIABILITY ISSUES FOR BLACK-BOX AI IN THE US WITH INSIGHTS FROM THE EU

To demonstrate the applicability and limitations of the current US liability framework in medical cases that involve black-box AI, this Part analyzes three hypothetical scenarios under US tort liability law and the current and newly proposed EU liability framework to determine who (if anyone) may be held liable for a person's injury. Scenario 1 focuses on an *autonomous* black-box AI (so its output is *not* reviewed or overseen by a human) that is used by a healthcare provider for patient treatment. Scenario 2 involves a *non-autonomous* black-box AI used by a healthcare provider, and Scenario 3 deals with a *direct-to-consumer* (DTC) black-box AI.²⁰⁹

A. SCENARIO 1: AUTONOMOUS BLACK-BOX USED BY A HEALTHCARE PROVIDER FOR PATIENT TREATMENT

Imagine a legally-marketed autonomous black-box AI that uses deep learning to read head computed tomography (CT) scans without the input of a radiologist is used by an individual or organizational healthcare

²⁰⁹ For more information on the different terminology (autonomous, non-autonomous, direct-to-consumer), *see supra* Section I.A. and B.2.

provider to treat patients.²¹⁰ If the AI reports a positive finding, the patient is referred to a specialist for further evaluation and treatment. However, negative CT scans are not reviewed further. In this Scenario, the black-box AI incorrectly reports a negative CT scan with no significant findings, which leads to a missed diagnosis and subsequent injury for the patient.

1. ANALYSIS UNDER CURRENT US TORT LIABILITY LAW

In this Scenario, the patient could potentially sue the manufacturer under product liability law and/or the individual or organizational healthcare providers under fault-based negligence law.

a. Manufacturer Liability

To recover against the manufacturer under either strict or negligent product liability law, the patient would need to prove that this autonomous black-box AI suffered from a design, manufacturing, or marketing defect that caused their injury.²¹¹

A *design defect* claim would require the patient to prove that the AI's design made it unreasonably dangerous.²¹² This will be difficult if the manufacturer designed this AI specifically to engage in noninterpretable and potentially unpredictable algorithmic reasoning to ultimately produce CT reports. This AI likely responded to vast amounts of data during the training process and, to some extent, *designed itself* using deep learning. Nevertheless, the manufacturer still had some control over the design of the AI's source algorithms, training, and validation and, thus, could be liable for design defects if these processes caused the AI to misread the CT. For example, if the manufacturer designed the AI to use poor-quality training data, it was likely foreseeable that the AI would produce poor-quality CT reports in accordance with the "garbage in, garbage out" adage. On the other hand, if this AI's uninterpretable and potentially unpredictable reasoning is

²¹⁰ See Press Release, U.S. Food & Drug Admin., *supra* note 41 (autonomous AI that diagnosis diabetic retinopathy); Nicole Wetsman, *The AI Imaging Tool Reads Chest X-Rays Without the Involvement of a Radiologist*, THE VERGE (Apr. 5, 2022), <https://www.theverge.com/2022/4/5/23011291/imaging-ai-autonomous-chest-xray-eu-fda> (autonomous AI that reads chest X-rays); Shammi Ramlakhan, et al., *Understanding and Interpreting Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning and Deep Learning in Emergency Medicine*, 39 EMERGENCY MED. J. 380, 380–84 (2022) (potential of AI to recognize fractures in X-rays).

²¹¹ See *supra* Section II.A. We assume for this section that the AI system would be considered a "product" subject to strict liability law. For negligent product liability, an additional requirement that the manufacturer's negligence caused the defect would apply.

²¹² See *supra* Section II.A.1.

a feature of its design, this unpredictability might factor into its usefulness, and the cost of eliminating this unpredictability may have a detrimental effect on the AI's accuracy, tilting risk-utility considerations against finding a design defect. Even assuming a design defect, the plaintiff would have to show that a reasonable alternative design existed at the time the AI was placed on the market. This would require the plaintiff to obtain and understand information surrounding the complex technical aspects of AI architecture, an evidentiary burden that would be extremely difficult to carry.²¹³

Liability for a *manufacturing defect* would require the plaintiff to prove that the black-box AI system was not operating as designed when it misread the CT scan.²¹⁴ For example, if the AI was designed to be trained with data from a diverse patient population but was instead trained with data from a homogenous patient population, this might be considered a manufacturing defect. The potentially "defective" data set might also be considered a component part if it was provided by a third party. Of course, if a physical hardware component caused the AI to produce an incorrect CT report, for example, a faulty connection component that disabled a crucial feature of the AI's algorithm, this might also be a manufacturing defect. However, if the AI was operating as originally designed by the manufacturer, it would likely not suffer from a manufacturing defect.

A *failure to warn claim* against the manufacturer would require the patient's injuries to be foreseeable.²¹⁵ While the manufacturer might be able to foresee that this AI could miss a positive finding on a CT scan generally, it may not be able to predict the specific risks that caused the AI to miss the CT finding in this patient's case. However, if the manufacturer was aware or became aware of the specific risks that caused the AI to produce this patient's inaccurate CT report, even after the AI was on the market, it would likely be liable for failing to warn of such risks. On the other hand, if the manufacturer issued warnings about the general risk that the AI may not produce an accurate CT report in every single case, it will likely not be liable for failing to warn of the more specific risk that manifested in this individual case if such a risk was unforeseeable because the manufacturer could not predict how the AI would respond in each individual case.

Even if the AI was defective, the manufacturer may have *several defenses*.²¹⁶ First if this black-box AI received PMA from the FDA, product liability claims would likely be preempted. Second, even if this AI took a

²¹³ See *supra* Section II.C.

²¹⁴ See *supra* Section II.A.2.

²¹⁵ See *supra* Section II.A.3.

²¹⁶ See *supra* Section II.A.4.

less stringent premarket review path and received only a 501(k) clearance, the manufacturer might still avoid product liability if its ability to autonomously read CT scan rendered it an unavoidably unsafe product that, despite “some risks, perhaps serious ones,” has the potential to “save lives and reduce pain and suffering.”²¹⁷ Third, if at the time the AI was manufactured, it complied with applicable safety regulation, and it was not technologically possible to design a less-risky and comparably beneficial AI to read CT reports, the manufacturer may avoid liability under the state-of-the-art defense. Fourth, if the manufacturer provided sufficient warnings to the individual or organizational healthcare provider that deployed the AI to read the patient’s CT scan, the provider’s decision to use the AI in the patient’s treatment may shield the manufacturer from liability under the LID. Finally, a host of subsequent actions by other parties that constitute misuse, alteration, modification, or negligence, might foreclose product liability for the manufacturer. This might include such things as the radiology technician’s failure to properly position the patient for the CT or the provider’s decision to use the CT scan in this patient’s treatment in contradiction to the manufacturer’s instructions.

b. Healthcare Provider Liability

A negligence claim based on the autonomous black-box AI’s missed finding would also face several challenges. First, the AI is performing actions that, if performed by a human radiologist, would be considered medical treatment—in this Scenario, reading CT scans and producing radiology reports.²¹⁸ Currently, AI is not capable of negligence because, unlike healthcare providers, they are not legal persons.²¹⁹

Although this AI is autonomous, the individual or organizational healthcare provider(s) that chose to use the AI might still be liable for injuries caused by the AI’s failure to report positive CT findings if they were negligent in using and/or implementing the AI into clinical care generally

²¹⁷ Brown, 751 P.2d at 479.

²¹⁸ See Mindy Nunez Duffourc & Dominick S. Giovanniello, *The Autonomous AI Physician: Medical Ethics and Legal Liability*, in *AI, LAW & BEYOND* (Henrique Sousa Antunes & Arlindo Oliveira eds., forthcoming 2023).

²¹⁹ See See Jason Chung & Amanda Zink, *Hey Watson - Can I Sue You for Malpractice? - Examining the Liability of Artificial Intelligence in Medicine*, 11 *ASIA PAC. J. HEALTH L. & ETHICS* 53 (2018) (“Courts have traditionally deemed it impossible for machines to have legal liability as they are not legal persons. . . . Regarding the human-centric categories, both negligence and vicarious liability as causes of action appear to require personhood.”).

or in this patient's treatment specifically.²²⁰ On the other hand, if neither provider's decision to use the AI nor their implementation of the AI in clinical practice was negligent, they may not be held liable for an injury caused by the AI's inaccurate CT report.²²¹ Even if the healthcare provider was negligent, for example, by using the AI in the wrong patient population, failing to train staff regarding the proper use and oversight of the system, or failing to update the system, it could still be difficult to prove that this negligence caused the AI's inaccurate CT report. Establishing a causal link between the provider's negligence and the AI's subsequent CT report might require the plaintiff to understand and evaluate highly technical aspects of the AI's deep-learning architecture.²²² Finally, the liability of a negligent provider in this Scenario could be reduced or barred by the negligence of other parties, including the patient.²²³ This might be the case, for example, if the patient was advised to follow up for further medical treatment and failed to do so if such failure caused or contributed to their injury remaining undiagnosed or untreated.

2. ANALYSIS UNDER THE CURRENT AND NEWLY PROPOSED EU LIABILITY FRAMEWORK

In this Scenario, the patient could potentially sue the manufacturer for product liability and/or the individual or organizational healthcare providers for fault-based medical liability under Member States' national law, which would incorporate the substantive legal principles set forth in the EU's Directives, specifically the current PLD, and the proposed PLD and AILD (once enacted and transposed into national law).

a. Manufacturer Liability

This autonomous black-box AI also challenges the EU's current product liability framework for manufacturers. Under the current PLD, if this AI is considered intangible software and is not embedded into a tangible product, it would not be considered a product.²²⁴

The patient has a better product liability claim under the newly proposed PLD. First, the proposed PLD explicitly includes software in its product definition.²²⁵ Second, the proposed PLD could shift some of the

²²⁰ See *supra* Section II.B.2.

²²¹ See Duffourc & Gerke, *supra* note 199.

²²² See *supra* Section II. B.3 and II.C.

²²³ See *supra* Section II.B.4.

²²⁴ See PLD art. 2. See also *supra* Section III.A.1.

²²⁵ See proposed PLD art. 4(1). See also *supra* Section III.B.1.

evidentiary burden associated with the complex technical aspects of the AI's architecture to the manufacturer, making it easier for the patient to obtain information and prove that the AI's missed CT finding was the result of a defect.²²⁶ Third, the PLD's recognition that both the AI's design and the relationship between the AI and its manufacturer are dynamic might help the patient prove a defect. For example, if this AI is not locked and has the ability to continuously learn, this factor might weigh in favor of finding it defective.²²⁷ Additionally, if the manufacturer failed to provide a necessary post-market update that would have prevented the AI from missing the positive CT finding, the AI might be considered defective under the proposed PLD, which recognizes the potential for the manufacturer to retain control over the AI after market entry. Finally, this AI could also be deemed defective under the proposed PLD if the manufacturer failed to comply with mandatory safety requirements, such as those set forth in the EU's AI Act and Medical Device Regulation.

Similar to US law, the manufacturer could, however, still escape liability even under the proposed PLD if the black-box nature of the AI's reasoning process made it impossible for the manufacturer to predict that AI would misread the CT scan. For example, the fact that this AI uses black-box technology to make decisions that the manufacturer may not be able to reasonably predict or prevent signals a lack of manufacturer control and weighs against finding a defect.²²⁸ Additionally, if the manufacturer fully complied with the applicable safety standards and the patient was appropriately informed of both medical and technical risks associated with using the AI, the missed CT finding may not be considered a product defect.²²⁹ Finally, the proposed PLD retains the state-of-the-art defense, which might allow the manufacturer to escape liability if the AI's missed CT finding resulted from a defect that the manufacturer could not have discovered when the AI was placed on the market.

A product liability claim based on negligence under either the current national fault-based liability law or national fault-based liability law with the proposed AILD would encounter many of the same challenges related to the product's design that make strict liability claims under the PLD challenging. Namely, it might be difficult to prove negligence in the product's design if the AI was designed to be uninterpretable and unpredictable and its reasoning process was unforeseeable. However, if the manufacturer was negligent in selecting the AI's training data, for example,

²²⁶ See proposed PLD art. 8(1). See also *supra* Section III.B.1.

²²⁷ See proposed PLD art. 6(1). See also *supra* Section III.B.1.

²²⁸ See *id.*

²²⁹ See *id.*

then the proposed AILD would entitle the patient to a presumption that the poor training data caused the AI's inaccurate CT report for this patient as long as it is reasonably likely that the negligence caused the AI's failure.²³⁰

b. Healthcare Provider Liability

Individual and organizational healthcare providers might also escape fault-based liability in the EU despite the proposed AILD's goal of facilitating fault-based liability claims in cases involving an AI-caused injury. This is because the proposed AILD would not alter the basic elements of proving fault under current national law, which for most Member States, as in the US, would require the patient to first prove that an individual or organizational healthcare provider failed to comply with an existing duty of care.²³¹ Since the AI itself is not considered a legal person, the patient must connect the AI's missed CT finding to the healthcare provider(s) that chose to use the AI in the patient's care. For example, if the healthcare provider used the AI in the wrong patient population, there would likely be a breach of the standard of care. However, if the healthcare provider's use, implementation, and oversight of the AI complied with its existing duties of care, for example, by following the manufacturer's instructions, properly training staff that use the AI, and monitoring the AI's performance, then the healthcare provider may also not be at fault.²³²

If the patient is able to establish fault by an individual or organizational healthcare provider, the AILD's evidentiary presumptions on causation would benefit the patient.²³³ Considering the above example of a breach stemming from the provider's use of the AI in the wrong patient population, the patient would benefit from a presumption that this breach caused the AI to miss a significant finding in the patient's CT scan as long as the missed finding was a "reasonably likely" result of using the AI in the wrong patient population.²³⁴ This presumption of causation will help reduce the barriers associated with obtaining and understanding evidence related to the complex technical inner-workings of the AI at the causation stage.

²³⁰ See proposed AILD art. 4(1). See also *supra* Section III.B.2

²³¹ See proposed AILD, Explanatory Memorandum, recital 23. See also *supra* Section III.B.2.

²³² See proposed AILD, art. 2(9), 4(1)–(3). See also *supra* Section III.B.2.

²³³ See proposed AILD art. 4(1).

²³⁴ *Id.*

B. SCENARIO 2: NON-AUTONOMOUS BLACK-BOX AI USED BY A HEALTHCARE PROVIDER

Imagine a legally-marketed non-autonomous black-box AI that quickly predicts the cause of acute respiratory failure in a patient presenting to the emergency room, a task that can be difficult for human physicians.²³⁵ A human physician then relies upon the AI's prediction to determine the appropriate emergency medical treatment. The AI predicts a diagnosis of pneumonia, but the patient was suffering from heart failure, and thus received the wrong treatment, which led to an injury.

1. ANALYSIS UNDER CURRENT US TORT LIABILITY LAW

In this Scenario, the patient could potentially sue the manufacturer under product liability law and/or the individual or organizational healthcare providers under fault-based negligence law.

a. Manufacturer Liability

The product liability analysis under US tort liability law in this Scenario is largely similar to the analysis discussed in Scenario 1.²³⁶ First, assuming that the AI is considered a product, a claim against the manufacturer for product liability will depend on the reason for the AI's wrong prediction. If, for example, the AI predicted an incorrect pneumonia diagnosis because the AI was either improperly designed to use a data set that was too small or improperly validated using the wrong patient population, then the manufacturer might be liable for a design defect. Additionally, the AI was designed to use a data set that was different than the data set actually used to train it, causing the final AI to operate differently than its intended design, then the manufacturer might be liable for a manufacturing defect. Finally, if the manufacturer failed to comply with monitoring, warning, or updating requirements, it might be liable for a marketing defect. On the other hand, if the AI was trained, validated, and functioning as designed to use a noninterpretable algorithmic reasoning to provide a prediction, the mere fact that the pneumonia prediction for this patient was incorrect is likely not enough to deem the product defective or the manufacturer negligent under the current product liability framework

²³⁵ See Sarah Jabbour et al., *Combining Chest X-Rays and Electronic Health Record (EHR) Data Using Machine Learning to Diagnose Acute Respiratory Failure*, 29 J. AM. MED. INFORMATICS ASS'N 160 (2022).

²³⁶ See *supra* Section IV.A.1.a.

under the same risk-utility considerations and potential defenses discussed in Scenario 1. However, in contrast to Scenario 1, since a physician directly oversees this non-autonomous system, an affirmative LID defense is more likely to be successful in this Scenario than in Scenario 1.²³⁷

b. Healthcare Provider Liability

For a patient to successfully sue a healthcare provider for medical malpractice in this case, they must first prove that the provider breached the standard of care. With regard to both individual and organizational healthcare providers, if we assume that they complied with all the standards, guidelines, and instructions, related to the use, implementation, and oversight of the AI, for example, properly selecting the AI for use in emergency care, ensuring proper training, instruction, oversight by competent staff, properly maintaining software, having proper policies related to the AI's use, the provider will likely not be negligent for using the AI in emergency care.

Similarly, the physician that relied on the AI's pneumonia prediction may not be negligent. Here, the AI predicted the cause of acute respiratory failure using complex algorithmic reasoning that is neither transparent nor interpretable to the human physician, making it impossible for them to understand the true basis for the AI's prediction.²³⁸ Further, although the physician oversaw the AI and was officially tasked with making the final "medical decision," they were not able to independently assess the accuracy of the AI's prediction prior to making the decision to treat the patient for pneumonia rather than heart failure.²³⁹ As a result, reliance on the AI's pneumonia prediction may not violate an applicable duty of care if the physician used this legally-marketed AI in accordance with its intended use and did not know and could not have known that the AI's prediction was incorrect.

2. ANALYSIS UNDER THE CURRENT AND NEWLY PROPOSED EU
LIABILITY FRAMEWORK

In this Scenario, the patient could potentially sue the manufacturer for product liability and/or the individual or organizational healthcare

²³⁷ See *supra* Section II.A.4.

²³⁸ Duffoure & Gerke, *supra* note 199.

²³⁹ Of course, it is also possible that the human provider is not capable of independently assessing the accuracy of the AI's decision at any point in time. This is particularly true if the AI provides an output that exceeds current human knowledge.

providers for fault-based medical liability under Member States' national law, which would incorporate the substantive legal principles set forth in the EU's Directives, specifically the current PLD, and the proposed PLD and AILD (once enacted and transposed into national law).

a. Manufacturer Liability

The analysis of product liability for this non-autonomous black-box AI under the current PLD and proposed PLD and AILD is largely the same as the analysis in Scenario 1.²⁴⁰ However, we highlight a few specific points for this Scenario. First, even under the proposed PLD's new test for determining defectiveness, the AI's inaccurate pneumonia prediction may not be considered a defect if it was the result of the AI's black-box algorithmic reasoning process, which the manufacturer could not have been able to predict or control. Second, the fact that this AI is non-autonomous may further remove it from the manufacturer's control and thus decrease the likelihood of finding a defect.²⁴¹ Third, if the manufacturer complied with all mandatory safety requirements, the likelihood considering the AI's inaccurate pneumonia prediction to be a defect under the proposed PLD, decreases further.

b. Healthcare Provider Liability

As in Scenario 1, the patient will only be able to recover if they can prove fault of a healthcare provider.²⁴² As in the US, if both the individual and organizational healthcare providers' use, implementation, and oversight of the AI did not violate any legal duties of care, it will be difficult for a patient to prove fault in connection with the provider's use of the AI in emergency care.²⁴³ Additionally, and again similar to the situation in the US, if this AI makes predictions by recognizing patterns in data that the human brain cannot discern or provides a time-sensitive prediction that the physician cannot make themselves, the physician's failure to recognize the incorrect prediction may not be considered a breach of a duty of care if they could not have known that the AI's pneumonia prediction was incorrect at the time they relied on it to prescribe emergency medical treatment.²⁴⁴

²⁴⁰ See *supra* Section IV.A.2.a.

²⁴¹ See proposed PLD, art. 6(1)(b), (e), (h).

²⁴² See *supra* Section IV.A.2.b.

²⁴³ See *id.*

²⁴⁴ Duffourc & Gerke, *supra* note 199.

Also, as discussed in Scenario 1, if the plaintiff is able to prove individual or organizational provider fault, the proposed AILD may provide them with an evidentiary presumption that the provider's fault caused the AI's incorrect pneumonia prediction²⁴⁵. However, this is only the case if the provider's fault preceded the AI's prediction, which would occur, for example, in this Scenario if the hospital was at fault by deciding to use the AI in the wrong patient population. Because the EC determined that claimants will not encounter the burden of proof difficulties in cases when "AI systems providing medical analysis or even suggestions for diagnosis and treatment, which are feeding into a decision on diagnosis and treatment, but [when] that decision is ultimately taken by a human physician," the AILD's evidentiary rules will not assist the patient if there is no fault that preceded the AI's inaccurate pneumonia prediction.²⁴⁶

C. SCENARIO 3: DIRECT-TO-CONSUMER BLACK-BOX AI

Imagine that a consumer, without consulting a doctor, turns to a DTC general-use black-box AI to answer the following health-related question at 9:00 a.m.:

Question:

I'm a 50-year old man that weighs 180 pounds. I take medication for high cholesterol and high blood pressure. I'm having heartburn, nausea, and shoulder pain. What might be wrong with me?

Response:

I'm sorry to hear that you're experiencing these symptoms. As an AI language model, I am not qualified to provide medical diagnoses or treatment advice. However, based on your symptoms, there are a few possible causes:

1. Acid reflux: The heartburn and nausea could be symptoms of acid reflux, which occurs when stomach acid flows back into the esophagus. This can cause a burning

²⁴⁵ See proposed AILD art. 4(1).

²⁴⁶ *Commission Staff Working Document, supra* note 176, § 2.2.

sensation in the chest, as well as nausea and vomiting.

2. Heart attack: Shoulder pain can sometimes be a symptom of a heart attack, especially if it is accompanied by chest pain, shortness of breath, and sweating. Given your age and medical history, it's important to take this possibility seriously and seek medical attention immediately if you experience these symptoms.

3. Gallbladder problems: Shoulder pain can also be a symptom of gallbladder problems, such as gallstones or inflammation of the gallbladder. This can cause nausea and vomiting as well.

It's important that you see a doctor as soon as possible to determine the cause of your symptoms and receive appropriate treatment. Your doctor may perform tests such as an electrocardiogram (ECG), blood tests, or imaging tests to help diagnose the underlying condition.²⁴⁷

The user in this Scenario interpreted the AI's numbered list as an indication that the first diagnosis listed was the most likely diagnosis. This put the user at ease, and they took some medication for heartburn and planned to visit the doctor during their afternoon work break, which for them was "as soon as possible." At 11:00 a.m., the user suffered an injury from a heart attack.

1. ANALYSIS UNDER CURRENT US LIABILITY LAW

In this Scenario, the consumer may be able to sue the manufacturer under strict or fault-based product liability law. Since there are no healthcare providers involved in this Scenario, there is no potential fault-based liability based on an individual or organizational healthcare provider's actions. Thus, the following analysis focuses exclusively on manufacturing liability.

Injuries caused by DTC general-use AI that provides medical information and advice also present challenges to the traditional product

²⁴⁷ OpenAI, ChatGPT May 24 Version, *Shoulder Pain and Heartburn* (originally generated on Apr. 21, 2023), <https://chat.openai.com/share/056a6055-0577-42be-bd23-c9528625c0ce>.

liability framework. Assuming that this DTC general-use black-box AI is a product subject to product liability law, the analysis of a *design defect* claim is largely similar to Scenarios 1 and 2.²⁴⁸ However, unlike the health-specific black-box AI in Scenarios 1 and 2, this general-use AI is not likely to be considered an unavoidably dangerous product in a design defect claim.²⁴⁹ As a result, it is less likely to pass a risk-utility test, particularly if it could have been better designed to avoid misleading consumers into believing that they are receiving personalized and reliable medical information and advice, for example, by refraining from providing answers to users' questions that seek an individualized medical diagnosis.

As discussed in Scenarios 1 and 2, the consumer may be able to prove a *manufacturing defect* if the data used to train the general-use AI was not the training data specified by the manufacturer's design.²⁵⁰ However, this will likely not be the case for a general-use AI that is designed to use vast amounts of data available on the internet generally rather than a health-specific AI that was designed, trained, and validated for a health-specific purpose.

A *failure to warn* claim may offer some protection to the consumer in this case. Warning users about its lack of medical expertise may be sufficient to warn users of the risks of relying on the AI's answers to health-related questions.²⁵¹ However, despite this AI's admission that it is "not qualified to provide medical diagnoses or treatment advice," it continued to do just that. A court may find that simply disclaiming that the information it provides is not medical advice does not magically exempt it from being medical advice or, at least, misleading the user into thinking that it is medical advice.²⁵² In fact, the recommendation to seek medical advice itself may be considered medical advice.²⁵³ If the user's reliance on the AI's medical advice, despite the AI warning, is a reasonably foreseeable misuse

²⁴⁸ See *supra* Sections IV.a.1.a and IV.b.1.a.

²⁴⁹ See *supra* Section II.A.4.

²⁵⁰ See *supra* Sections IV.a.1.a and IV.b.1.a.

²⁵¹ *Will ChatGPT Transform Healthcare?*, *supra* note 64.

²⁵² See *Matter of Hodge*, 407 P.3d 613, 644 (Kan. 2017) (letter stating that an attorney was not providing legal advice did not preclude their legal advice from being legal advice); *Bennett v. Bureau of Pro. & Occupational Affs.*, 214 A.3d 728, 737 (Pa. Comm. Ct. 2019) (a disclaimer does not cure misleading representations); *Khan v. BDO Seidman, LLP*, 948 N.E.2d 132, 154 (Ill. 2011), *aff'd sub nom. Khan v. Deutsche Bank AG*, 978 N.E.2d 1020 (boilerplate disclaimer of no fiduciary relationship insufficient when party served as broker and gave investment advice).

²⁵³ *Doctor's Co. v. McDonough*, No. 01-00-00741-CV, 2002 WL 2024260, at *3 (Tex. Ct. App. Aug. 30, 2002). See *Ghee v. USABLE Mut. Ins. Co.*, No. 1200485, 2023 WL 2720996 at *8 (Ala. Mar. 31, 2023) ("advising participant to return to hospital" was medical advice).

of the AI or if the manufacturer became aware of an unreasonable risk for users who relied on the AI's answers and failed to update its warnings, the manufacturer may be liable for a marketing defect.²⁵⁴

Finally, we note that even if this AI is considered defective, the manufacturer may be able to avoid strict product liability by proving that the user either (1) misused the system by relying on medical advice or information "in direct contravention of the product's warnings and instructions" if this misuse is not reasonably foreseeable, or (2) had subjective knowledge of the specific risks associated with relying on the AI's medical information or advice and chose to assume that risk. The manufacturer may also be able to avoid or reduce their liability by showing that the consumer's reliance on the AI's output was objectively unreasonable (or negligent) in either negligent product liability cases or in jurisdictions that allow a comparative allocation of fault in strict liability cases.

2. ANALYSIS UNDER THE CURRENT AND NEWLY PROPOSED EU LIABILITY FRAMEWORK

In this Scenario, the patient could potentially sue the manufacturer for product liability under Member States' national law, which would incorporate the substantive legal principles set forth in the EU's Directives, specifically the current PLD and proposed PLD (once enacted and transposed into national law). Again, since no healthcare providers are involved in this Scenario, there is no potential fault-based liability under Member States' national law based on an individual or organizational healthcare provider's actions. Thus, the following analysis focuses exclusively on manufacturing liability.

Under the current PLD, this DTC AI is less likely to be considered a product subject to strict product liability because it is probably not embedded into a tangible product.²⁵⁵ Since the proposed PLD would consider this AI a product, it provides a better basis for the plaintiff to recover under strict liability framework. The AI in this Scenario presents the user with a sophisticated, seemingly individualized response to a user-specific health question, which a court might weigh in finding a defect under the product's presentation factor.²⁵⁶ Additionally, its instruction to the user "to see a doctor as soon as possible" might also weigh in favor of finding a

²⁵⁴ See *supra* Section II.A.2.

²⁵⁵ See *supra* PLD art. 2. See also *supra* Section II.A.1.

²⁵⁶ See PLD art. 6(1)(a); proposed PLD art. 6(1)(a); See also *supra* Sections III.a.1 and II.b.1.

defect if the user's interpretation of this instruction, that is to see a doctor during a work break hours later, is considered reasonable. Finally, if this is an adaptive DTC AI, its ability to continuously learn will also weigh in favor of finding it defective.

On the other hand, under the proposed PLD, if the court finds that following the AI's instruction would have required a different response by the user—that is, immediate consultation with a human doctor—this might weigh against finding a defect. Additionally, the user's reliance on the AI's response to this medical question, despite the AI's warning that it is not qualified to provide medical advice, might be considered a reasonably foreseeable misuse of the product weighing in favor of finding a defect.²⁵⁷ However, if the court finds that the user's reliance on the AI's output, despite its disclosure that it cannot provide medical advice, was unreasonable, the AI may not be considered defective in this case.²⁵⁸ Third, the product's ability to continually learn—if not locked—will likely weigh in favor of finding a defect.²⁵⁹ Fourth, if the manufacturer complied with all mandatory safety requirements, this would likely weigh against finding a defect.²⁶⁰

A negligent product liability claim under Member States' national fault-based liability law would likely involve similar considerations when judging whether the manufacturer's behavior in designing, manufacturing, and marketing this DTC AI breaches a duty of care.²⁶¹ For example, if the manufacturer's failure to design the system to refrain from providing any response to a user's request for individualized medical advice is considered unreasonable, a manufacturer may face liability under a Member's State's fault-based liability law. Finally, the proposed AILD would provide the injured user with an evidentiary presumption that the manufacturer's fault caused the AI's given medical advice in response to the user's question, but the user would still have to prove that the AI's response caused, or partially caused, his injury under the Member States' burden of proof rules.²⁶²

V. LESSONS LEARNED FROM THE EU'S APPROACH TO BLACK-BOX AI LIABILITY

A comparison of the EU and US liability frameworks for medical injuries caused by black-box AI systems and the application of these frameworks in the specific Scenarios involving black-box AI systems

²⁵⁷ See proposed PLD art. 6(1)(b). See also *supra* Section III.b.1.

²⁵⁸ See sources cited *id.*

²⁵⁹ See proposed PLD art. 6(1)(c). See also *supra* Section III.b.1.

²⁶⁰ See proposed PLD art. 6(1)(f). See also *supra* Section III.b.1.

²⁶¹ See *supra* Section III.a.2.

²⁶² See proposed AILD art. 4(1), recital 15. See also *supra* Section III.b.2.

reveals several lessons that the US can learn from the EU's approach to AI liability, and specifically, liability for medical injuries caused by black-box AI systems. This Part first argues for the relevance of the EU's approach and then draws lessons for the US.

A. RELEVANCE OF THE EU'S APPROACH

As demonstrated in Sections II to IV, remarkably similar principles govern liability for manufacturers and healthcare providers in the US and EU. While they both recognize fault-based (or negligent) manufacturer liability, both jurisdictions also take a stricter approach to liability for injuries caused by defective products. Both jurisdictions also consider consumer expectations and risk/utility factors to judge whether a product is defective in design. With regard to healthcare provider liability, both jurisdictions take fault-based approaches and will generally only impose liability when the individual or organizational healthcare provider breached a duty of care. Although there are some differences in the way the jurisdictions (even within the EU) approach evidentiary issues, including the burden and standard of proof, the common core of strict product liability for manufacturers and fault-based medical liability for healthcare providers remains. This, combined with common liability challenges that black-box AI poses in both jurisdictions, exemplified by the comparative analysis of the hypotheticals in Section IV, provides a compelling reason to pay attention to the EU's approach to liability for AI-caused injuries.

The EU is certainly ahead of the US when it comes to initiatives to update the legal framework to address new liability issues raised by AI. Generally, the EC recognizes that “[it] is important that victims of accidents of products and services including emerging digital technologies like AI do not enjoy a lower level of protection compared to similar other products and services, for which they would get compensation under national tort law.”²⁶³ The newly proposed PLD and proposed AILD represent the EC's attempts to remedy potential liability gaps and ensure legally trustworthy AI through ex-post liability rules.²⁶⁴

The EU's general approach to AI liability in the proposed Directives addresses some of the challenges that arise with the use of black-box AI for healthcare, but it also falls short in some regards. An analysis of both the successes and the shortcomings of the EU's approach, when applied in the healthcare context, provides valuable lessons for the US. In terms of successes, both proposed EU Directives make progress toward the EU's

²⁶³ *Report From the Commission to the European Parliament*, *supra* note 176.

²⁶⁴ *See generally* proposed PLD & proposed AILD.

goal of ensuring trustworthy AI by (1) directly addressing unique risks posed by AI in their respective no-fault and fault-based liability approaches and (2) mitigating the information asymmetry through increased access to evidence and decreased burdens of proof for claimants.²⁶⁵ As for shortcomings, the PLD and AILD in combination with national law still fail to provide a workable liability framework for some medical injuries caused by black-box AI. This is because the AI may not be considered defective under the PLD, and there may be no breach of a duty of care by a legally responsible person upon which to base liability.²⁶⁶ As shown in Section IV, similar gaps might emerge in the US under the existing tort framework governing manufacturer and healthcare provider liability.²⁶⁷

B. LESSONS LEARNED FROM THE EU

The EU's recent attempts to preemptively tackle challenges related to liability for AI-caused injuries provide four valuable lessons for US stakeholders involved with the creation and use of black-box AI as they inevitably face a case involving liability for medical injury caused by this rapidly developing technology.

Lesson 1: A broad approach to AI liability fails to provide solutions to some challenges posed by black-box AI in healthcare.

Both countries face the colossal task of adapting legal systems to accommodate the new demands that accompany the rapid development and integration of AI technology in various sectors of society. The EU is on the right path to addressing AI-related safety concerns through both ex-ante regulation and ex-post liability rules, but the diversity of AI architecture and applications demands a more dynamic approach to liability for AI-caused injuries, particularly in the health sector. The EU's proposed PLD and AILD follow the proposed AI Act, which seeks to protect fundamental rights and ensure safety in connection with AI through ex-ante regulation.²⁶⁸ The combination of regulatory and liability-based approaches to AI reflects the EC's view that "[s]afety and liability are two sides of the same coin: they apply at different moments and reinforce each other."²⁶⁹ While this general approach to AI regulation and liability is commendable, the EU's failure to

²⁶⁵ See Duffourc & Gerke, *supra* note 199.

²⁶⁶ See *id.* for more information.

²⁶⁷ See Duffourc, *supra* note 17, at 4.

²⁶⁸ See generally proposed AI Act.

²⁶⁹ Proposed AILD, Explanatory Memorandum.

consider the unique risks posed by black-box AI in different industries, i.e., healthcare versus autonomous vehicles, leads to broad regulatory and liability rules that often fail to address crucial risks and leave worrying liability gaps.²⁷⁰

Lesson 2: Traditional concepts of human fault pose significant challenges in cases involving black-box AI.

In both jurisdictions, it may be difficult for claimants to connect AI-caused injuries to the fault of a party that can be held legally responsible under the current liability framework. While the EU has recognized that “[t]he processes running in AI systems cannot all be measured according to duties of care designed for human conduct,” the proposed AILD fails to address the largest obstacle to fault-based liability for black-box AI: proving fault vis-à-vis the non-compliance with an existing duty of care.²⁷¹ Under the proposed AILD, unless a presumption of fault arises from a defendant’s failure to disclose court-ordered evidence, the claimant still bears the burden of proving that a natural or legal person failed to comply with a duty of care under Member States’ national law that is “reasonably likely” to have influenced an AI’s injury-causing output.²⁷² Unfortunately, the opacity, complexity, and/or autonomy of black-box AI can cause damage that could not have been predicted or prevented by a legal person’s actions or omissions, completely severing the “fault” of the AI from potentially legally responsible persons associated with its use.

Lesson 3: Product liability frameworks must consider the unique features of black-box AI.

In both jurisdictions, black-box AI challenges the traditional product liability framework because it does not always present and function like a traditional product. First, black-box AI may not be considered a product subject to product liability claims. The EU solved this problem by explicitly clarifying that software is a “product” subject to liability under the proposed PLD.²⁷³

²⁷⁰ For more information regarding liability gaps in EU, see Duffoure & Gerke, *supra* note 199.

²⁷¹ See *Commission Report on Liability for Artificial Intelligence and Other Emerging Digital Technologies* (2019), <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2838/573689>; proposed AILD, recital 23.

²⁷² See proposed AILD art. 4(1)(b).

²⁷³ See proposed PLD art. 4(1).

Second, unlike traditional products, manufacturers may be able to maintain control and influence over a black-box AI's behavior following market entry, making market entry as the temporal reference to judge a product's defectiveness unsuitable for some black-box AI. In the EU, the proposed PLD recognizes the ability of software, including black-box AI, to change after market entry by expanding the scope of liability to include products still under the "manufacturer's control" rather than focusing solely on market entry.²⁷⁴ The PLD also integrates the continuous self-learning characteristic of adaptive algorithms as a characteristic affecting whether the product is considered "defective."²⁷⁵

Finally, it can be difficult to determine when a black-box AI is defective under the traditional framework. The proposed PLD's test for defectiveness makes some progress toward addressing the unique capabilities of AI, but it still fails to provide workable criteria for determining product "defectiveness" for some black-box AI technologies. The proposed PLD hinges defectiveness on a finding that the product "does not provide the safety which the public at large is entitled to expect, taking all circumstances into account."²⁷⁶ The proposed PLD also lists circumstances, including the ability of algorithms to continuously learn, which might weigh in favor of finding black-box AI defective.²⁷⁷ On the other hand, it considers the manufacturer's control over the product, compliance with safety requirements, and expectations of end-users, all of which may weigh against finding a black-box AI defective.²⁷⁸ Even when a product is considered defective, the proposed PLD provides an exemption to liability when the manufacturer could not have discovered the defect under the "objective state of scientific and technical knowledge."²⁷⁹

Lesson 4: Evidentiary rules should address the difficulties that claimants will face in obtaining evidence and proving causation.

In both jurisdictions, it may be difficult for plaintiffs to obtain evidence and satisfy evidentiary burdens in some cases involving an AI-caused injury because the technical inner workings of the black-box AI are highly complex and opaque. The proposed PLD's evidentiary rules can assist claimants with both obtaining evidence from manufacturers and

²⁷⁴ *See id.* art. 4(5).

²⁷⁵ *See id.* art. 6(1)(c).

²⁷⁶ *See id.* art. 6(1).

²⁷⁷ *Id.*

²⁷⁸ *Id.*

²⁷⁹ *See id.* art. 10(e).

proving defectiveness in cases involving complex black-box AI.²⁸⁰ The proposed AILD's evidentiary rules also address some of the concerns about information asymmetry by making evidence more accessible in claims involving high-risk systems and the burden of proof less demanding in many claims involving any type of AI.²⁸¹

CONCLUSION

This Article is the first that provided a comprehensive roadmap of liability for black-box AI in healthcare in the US and EU and a comparative legal methodology to identify important lessons for the US from the newly proposed EU approach. In Part I, we explained crucial features of black-box AI and outlined the landscape of current and future uses of black-box AI in the health sector. Part I identified how and why black-box AI technology presents both benefits and risks when used for health-related purposes and described that these benefits and risks are unique because they stem from unique features of the AI's design that are not typical of traditional consumer products and medical devices. As a result, medical injuries caused by black-box AI challenge the traditional liability framework in both the US and EU.

In Part II, we identified the current framework that would govern liability for manufacturers and individual and organizational healthcare providers in cases involving medical injuries caused by black-box AI in the US. When considering the current framework in the context of the unique risks presented by black-box AI systems, we revealed that there are critical liability concerns that manifest when some black-box AI systems cause medical injuries. We identified three valuable takeaways: (1) black-box AI challenges the legal standards by which products are deemed defective, (2) injuries caused by black-box AI cannot always be sufficiently connected to the fault of a legally responsible party, and (3) claimants who suffer a medical injury involving black-box AI may face significant evidentiary struggles.

In Part III, we identified the current and proposed framework governing liability for manufacturers and individual and organizational healthcare providers in cases involving medical injuries caused by black-box AI in the EU. Laying out the current framework in the context of black-box AI revealed that the EU and US encounter similar liability challenges when faced with the unique risks posed by black-box AI in large part

²⁸⁰ *See id.* art. 8(1), art. 9(4), art. 9(2).

²⁸⁰ *See id.* art. 8(1), 9(4).

²⁸¹ *Id.*

because both jurisdictions' liability frameworks are grounded in similar principles. We set forth the EU's new approach to liability for AI-caused injuries in the proposed PLD and AILD and analyzed these proposed liability rules in the context of black-box medical AI. We concluded the EU's approach to liability addresses (and fails to address) some of the liability challenges that both jurisdictions face as a result of black-box AI in healthcare, which entails important lessons for the US.

In Part IV, we discovered valuable insights from the EU's approach to AI liability by analyzing liability in three hypothetical scenarios involving a medical injury caused by black-box AI under both current US and current and newly proposed EU law. The comparative analysis revealed that the EU's proposed Directives successfully tackle some common liability challenges by (1) including AI in the scope of its definition of a product in the proposed PLD, (2) considering the dynamic nature of AI-driven products when determining whether a product is defective under the proposed PLD, and (3) adjusting evidentiary rules in some cases to help claimants who suffer AI-caused injuries under the proposed PLD and proposed AILD. However, our analysis also revealed that liability gaps can manifest in both jurisdictions when a medical injury results from a healthcare provider's use of an autonomous black-box AI (Scenario 1), a nonautonomous black-box AI (Scenario 2), and a consumer's use of a general black-box generative AI (Scenario 3). We concluded that these gaps are likely to occur when the AI's noninterpretable reasoning process produces an injury-causing output, and the following are true: (1) the AI was functioning as designed by the manufacturer, (2) the manufacturer complied with safety regulations relating to the AI's development and marketing, and (3) individual and organizational healthcare providers were reasonable in their use, selection, and implementation of the AI and could not have reasonably known that the AI's output was incorrect. We also concluded that black-box AI's complex architecture and operation present evidentiary challenges for injured claimants even with the newly proposed EU approach, particularly in meeting their burden of proving fault and causation.

In Part V, we identified lessons learned from the EU's approach to AI liability in the context of medical injuries caused by black-box AI. We found that the EU's approach is relevant to the US because the liability frameworks in both jurisdictions operate under similar legal principles and face common legal challenges when confronted with black-box AI in the healthcare domain. We argued that four main lessons can be learned from the EU's approach that are relevant for stakeholders in the US, who will likely encounter these common challenges. First, a broad approach to AI liability fails to provide solutions to some challenges posed by black-box

AI in healthcare. Second, traditional concepts of human fault pose significant challenges in cases involving black-box AI. Third, product liability frameworks must consider the unique features of black-box AI. Fourth, evidentiary rules should address the difficulties that claimants will face in cases involving medical injuries caused by black-box AI.

The possible benefits and consequences of black-box AI in healthcare are significant. Now is the time for stakeholders in the US to give serious consideration to the potential liability associated with the use of black-box AI in the health sector. Understanding the current liability framework and its limitations is crucial to ensure consumer and patient safety and to encourage the continued development and deployment of beneficial black-box AI in healthcare. This understanding should also consider the EU's newly proposed approach to liability for medical injuries for black-box AI to glean important lessons from the EU's attempts to solve similar liability challenges.

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